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MASTER OF ARTS IN NURSING

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**FACTORS INFLUENCING ENHANCED RECOVERY AND LENGTH OF STAY
AMONG SURGERY PATIENTS IN A SPECIALIST HOSPITAL IN THE KINGDOM
OF SAUDI ARABIA**

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30 August 2022

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Acceptance Page:

This Special Project titled: “**FACTORS INFLUENCING ENHANCED RECOVERY AND LENGTH OF STAY AMONG SURGERY PATIENTS IN A SPECIALIST HOSPITAL IN THE KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

Grace D. Catulay, motivated and with a strong desire to explore and expand her knowledge horizon, she has recently completed her Master of Arts in Nursing degree major in Adult Health Nursing in University of the Philippines- Open University. After few years of gaining her bachelor's degree in nursing from Colegio de San Agustin Bacolod, she has practiced nursing profession for 21 years and spend most of her career development in a tertiary/specialized Medical Facility in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. She was an Outpatient Clinic Nurse for 16 years and is currently a Clinical Nurse Coordinator in Enhanced Recovery After Surgery Program since 2019 in this prestigious government hospital in Eastern Province of the Kingdom.

In all recognitions and awards along her career, cited as the Best Nurse Award was one that stands out, given to her in 2014 as award of excellence from department of surgery on their first annual resident recognition day. The most recent award of appreciation she has received, is the participation in simulation training of staff nurses for early ambulation of ERAS patient in AICU as part of implementation process of the program to be a pioneer in the whole Kingdom. Grace also holds a Nurse Specialist category of license to practice nursing awarded by Saudi Commission and Health Specialty.

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Abstract

Enhanced Recovery After Surgery was first implemented in 2010 and became known worldwide as a multimodal care pathway with the aim to enhance recovery of patients that have undergone major surgeries. In the specialist hospital here in Saudi Arabia, it was first implemented in 2019.

This correlational study was conducted to determine the demographics of the patients, to ascertain the relationship between influencing factors and post-operative complication to the length of stay, and the incidence of post-operative complications among gyne-oncology surgery patients under ERAS protocol.

As the study has revealed, all age group in the study, from young adults, middle age and older adult participants under ERAS protocol, stayed within almost the same length of days in the hospital. It was also found that patients with minimal invasive surgery have faster full recovery versus open surgery. Carbohydrate loading has also showed that it has great impact in the early recovery thus shorten the length of stay of post-operative patients. On the other hand, multimodal analgesia, early nutrition and early ambulation was found significant in relation to shorter hospital stay.

PONV (post-operative nausea and vomiting) is claimed in studies to be the most common post-operative complication in all ages. It has affected some of the participants in varied frequency, intensity and time of manifestations, some within 24 hours and others after 24 hours. Hospital length of stay was greatly affected as data showed average of 80% full improvement on patients without PONV and an average of 20% partial improvement to participants with PONV. Post-operative nausea and vomiting definitely affects negatively total patient outcome when the data showed 3.8 days hospital stay on patients affected and 2.9 days

on unaffected patients.

It is apparent that quality outcome in ERAS implementation will only be achieved with strict compliance to the standard protocol.

Keywords: Enhanced Recovery, Nursing, Surgery Patients

Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Multiple studies regarding improved patient outcomes with ERAS has been already published showing significant difference in comparison to conventional surgical process. The impact of ERAS program in patient outcomes among health institutions have inspired this tertiary Specialist Hospital in KSA to adapt it, and utilize the unique standardized method of perioperative care, based on the best quality evidence towards the goal to achieve enhanced recovery, reduced post-operative complication rates and shorten hospital length of stay.

As ERAS program was implemented in this tertiary hospital , influencing factors were identified that is believed to affect the outcome. These are Age, type of surgery, pre-operative fasting and carbohydrate loading, type of analgesia, early ambulation and early nutrition. These are variables that has something to do with shorter patient stay in the hospital and lesser post-operative complications. Furthermore, compliance especially in the elements of ERAS specific to the influencing factors mentioned, can increase patient and surgical outcomes, patient and staff satisfaction and low cost.

When ERAS was implemented in the specialist hospital, it was observed that length of stay and post-operative complications has lessen dramatically. However, some healthcare providers are not motivated to comply with the implementation since there is no evidence to prove that it is beneficial. Compliance rate had remained static since there are staff that does not adhere to follow the protocol.

In this sense, feedback is very important to influence their level of compliance. As this study finds out and reveal how the influencing factors is correlated to length of stay, and how length of stay has improved, it would be easy to convey the message and encourage everyone to improve compliance in implementing ERAS protocol with the aim to achieve outstanding outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

This a correlational study between influencing factors and length of stay among Gyne-oncology surgery patients under ERAS protocol in the specialist hospital in KSA.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the profile of the respondents according to:
 - a. Age
 - b. Type of Surgery
 - c. Pre-operative fasting and Carbo loading
 - d. Type of analgesia
 - e. Early mobilization
 - f. Early nutrition
2. What is the length of stay of patients
3. What is the relationship between influencing factors and length of stay
 - a. Age
 - b. Type of surgery
 - c. Pre-operative fasting and carbo loading
 - d. Type of analgesia
 - e. Early mobilization
 - f. Early nutrition

4. What are the complications that occurred post-operatively

Significance of the Study

This correlational study is beneficial to nursing workforce. It is proven that post-operative patient under ERAS protocol recovers faster with lesser post-operative complications, shorter hospital length of stay, and post-operative patients gain physical function early. Therefore, the need of nurses assistance to meet the patient's daily needs will be lessen. The burden of nurses will be minimal, specific to assisting patients to get out of bed, change patient gown, assisting patient to the toilet, which will take place only within a matter of two to three days after surgery. Fast patient recovery progress allows nurses to work on other important tasks.

It is also beneficial to patients themselves, since they regain their physical function and mobility early. They can function alone without the help of others as they usually do before the surgery. This allows them to quickly reclaim their confidence, control of the situation and live their life normally again.

The institution also benefits from this, since low incident of post-operative complications and hospital length of stay will cut down use of resources, thus lower the hospital costs. Hospital beds will be free up early and will be able to accommodate more waiting patients for surgery.

The result of this study will also enlighten healthcare workers involved in patient care, in terms of favourable effects of ERAS protocol applied completely and meticulously to surgical patients.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This correlation study is mainly focused on gyne-oncolgy surgery patient population under ERAS program in a specialist hospital in KSA. The data was collected from patients qualified (as per inclusion criteria) to participate in the study. It may not cover other or possible significant points in different surgical areas, and the findings may not generalize to other patient population of different surgical specialties.

The evidence of lower hospital length of stay uncovered from the study will give insight and convince more health practitioners/surgeons that ERAS protocol is worth applying to other group of surgical specialties within or outside of this institution.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Related Literature

What is ERAS? It is a treatment program based on the best available evidence based practice and patient care, and is designed to achieve early recovery for patients undergoing major surgery. A paradigm shift from conventional to multidisciplinary and multimodal perioperative care pathway that promotes faster recovery while maintaining quality patient care and optimum surgical outcomes.

History of ERAS. Enhanced Recovery After Surgery started in 2001 by Ken Fearon and Olle Ljungqvist as a collaborative study group on peri-operative care. It was called ERAS study group comprised of leading surgical groups from UK, Sweden, Denmark, Norway, and Netherlands. As the group examines the process of change from tradition to best practice when they found out that there was a variety of traditions in use in different units and discovered that there was a great discrepancy between the actual practice and what is known to be the best practice. Many publications data has been shown in the beginning such as evidence-based consensus protocol for patients undergoing colonic surgery (Fearon et al, 2005), followed by the publication of data showing that just adding a protocol was not sufficient to change practice to ERAS (Maessen et al., 2007), and ERAS continued to grow more.

Incidence of Surgical Complications after Gynecological surgery

Post-operative Ileus. Research information is limited in Saudi Arabia. There

is almost no available data regarding post-operative paralytic ileus. However, in one study done in Saudi Arabia, they reported that out of 30 cases (11.4%), there is only one case of small bowel obstruction (Alharbi et al, 2020). In general, there is as high as 30% of women who have undergone open gynecologic surgeries have developed post-operative ileus (Bakkum-Gamez et al, 2012). Exposure to opioids, fluid balance, extent of peritoneal disease and complexity of surgery, receipt of transfusion, and post-operative abdomino-pelvic complications are known to be the factors that influence return of bowel function.

Interventions that decrease the risk of post-operative ileus include minimally invasive surgery, early feeding, consumption of coffee and gum chewing. It is concluded in the study entitled *A Prospective Controlled Trial of Early Postoperative Oral Intake Following Major Abdominal Gynecologic Surgery*, that hospital length of stay is decreased in patients undergoing abdominal surgery that had early post-operative oral intake (Schilder et al., 1997).

Laparoscopy as well minimize the risk of POI since it is much safer in terms of short-term outcomes and has fewer moderate to severe post-operative adverse events which leads to less complications and shorter hospital stay (Walker et al, 2009). Consumption of coffee after colectomy was safe and was also associated with a reduced time to first bowel action.

It was reported in a randomized clinical trial in post colectomy patients that the time to the first bowel movement was significantly shorter with patients who consume coffee than the patients who take water (Gungorduk et al., 2017). In addition, a randomized trial was done for chewing gum. It was set out that it is safe and lowers the incidence of POI and nausea in post laparotomy

gynecologic surgery patients (Jernigan et al., 2014).

Surgical Site Infection. In gynecologic oncology patients undergoing a laparotomy, 20-30% has experienced surgical site infection. It is associated with increased patient morbidity, mortality and health care expenditures (Lissovoy et al., 2009).

In one study done by Bharatnur et al. (2018), incidence of SSI was found in 52 out of 285 women (46%). The risk was noted in patients who are Over 50 of age, 4 times higher in risk with clean contaminated wounds compared to clean wounds and increasing the risk up to 7 times in case of dirty wounds. Other factors noted to be significantly associated with SSI are BMI, midline incision, and mattress suture. Predisposing factors includes presence of previous scar, intra operative adhesions, weaker scar and poor healing. Comorbidities that influence SSI's are Diabetes Mellitus, Anemia, and Hypertension.

In the study conducted in King Abdulaziz University Hospital in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, in 251 women who met the inclusion criteria, 199 (79%) had an abdominal hysterectomy (AH), including 22 who had a subtotal hysterectomy. Fifty-two (21%) had a vaginal hysterectomy (VH), including 3 patients who had a laparoscopic-assisted VH. 9.7% (n=24) and 20.3% (n=51) of the total population had intra-operative and post-operative complications but none was reported to have surgical site infection (Sait et al, 2008).

In another study done in patients who undergo Myomectomy in Saudi Arabia, the researchers asserts that the most common complications after surgery are hemorrhage, Pulmonary embosism, urinary tract infection, and Groin hematoma. There is no case of SSI among 25 (9.5%) cases of post-operative

complications from the total sample size of 263 women (Alharbi et al., 2020).

The intervention of implementing SSI reduction bundle to patients undergoing longer operations and in those with increased blood loss is effective and is associated with significant reduction in 30-day SSIs (schiavone et al., 2017). Surgical site infection bundle includes antimicrobial prophylaxis, skin preparation, prevention of hypothermia, avoidance of drains and tubes, and control of perioperative hyperglycemia. Evidence is increasing showing that ERAS implementation is safe, feasible and associated with improved outcomes by reduced complications and shortened length of stay (Pedziwiatr et al., 2018).

Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting. Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) is a common complication of anesthesia and surgery. It is considered the most common cause of morbidity following anesthesia and has significant effects on patient satisfaction and cost. In the study conducted by (Okafur, Amucheazi, Ewah, & Obioma, 2010) on 300 obstetrical and gynaecological patients, twelve women vomited within forty-eight hours of anesthesia (12/300 or 4.0%). Nine patients vomited in the gynaecological population (9/112) or 8% of the gynaecological population and (3/186) or 1.6% in the obstetric population.

ERAS Implementation.

The Committee on Gynecologic Practice (2018) of American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologist has concluded in their committee opinion publication that ERAS should be strongly encouraged to the institutions since it has rendered benefits across gynecologic surgeries. ERAS pathways has proceeded to rapid surgical recovery, shorter length of stay, greater patient satisfaction and decreased costs. They also deduced that with collaboration from

all members of surgical team, potential improvement in patient care and health care delivery system that remarkably relies on successful ERAS pathway implementation will be achieved. Glaser et al. (2018), International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics wrote that the evidence-based components of ERAS along with successful implementation all through perioperative period, enables gynecologic patients to recover and return to normal functions quickly.

ERAS on Length of Stay and Complication Rate

There is a research study at Mayo Clinic, that has shown a decreased length of stay in patients who have undergone complex cytoreductive procedures, a 3 day reduction in median length of stay (from 8-5 days) with similar report of LOS after 3 years (Glaser et al, 2018). Another study made in Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology in Sweden reports a significant reduction in length of stay in the study population from mean 2.6 days to 2.3 days after introduction of ERAS with complication rate of 5% vs. 3.5% in primary stay and 12% vs. 15% within 30 days after discharge (Wijk et al., 2014).

Retrospectively, hospital length of stay of post-operative patients in the specialist hospital prior ERAS implementation is (N=21) 4.1 days, while Length of stay after pilot implementation of ERAS was (N=8) 3.2 days.

INFLUENCING FACTORS

Age. A study was made to report perioperative morbidity and mortality rates in elderly women resulted to the conclusion that post-operative complications do not occur frequently but may increase their risk in undergoing gynecologic surgery (Toglia et al., 2003). However, a conclusion of the study

made to see the association of age with postoperative complications to a total of 22,214 women who went for gynecologic surgery, reported that women over 80 years old has higher risk of having a major post-operative complications after gynecologic procedures (Erekson et al., 2011).

Type of Surgery

- a. Minimally Invasive Surgery.** It is known that this modality is less invasive than traditional surgical practice and it has proven to provide improvement in patient outcomes by reducing hospital stays and perioperative complications (Stewart et al., 2017). Furthermore, as this current knowledge, technique and experience continue to improve, a better oncologic outcomes and enhanced patient satisfaction without compromising oncologic results is achievable (Mori et al., 2013).

- b. Open Surgery.** Conversion from laparoscopic surgery to open surgery was associated with moderate or severe adhesive disease and increasing specimen weight. However, conversion is associated with increased rates of surgical site infection, blood transfusion, severe sepsis, and reoperation (Lim et al., 2016). In addition, a prospective, randomized, controlled trial was conducted comparing an enhanced recovery after surgery protocol with routine postoperative care among women undergoing laparotomy on the gynecologic oncology service and resulted to no significant reduction in length of stay (Dickson et al., 2017).

Pre-operative Fasting and Carbohydrate Loading

In the study conducted by (Hill & Miller, 2015), they concluded that pre-

operative carbohydrate loading given to patient up to 2 hours has good evidence and widely supported by professional societies for nutrition and should be implemented strictly by the clinical team. It is further affirmed in their study that the time has come for consistent metabolic preparation of patient in the pre-operative period through delivery of carbohydrate loading in order to achieve improved surgical outcome.

Type of analgesia

In the study entitled “Changing from Epidural to multi modal analgesia” conducted by (Chilvers, Nguyen, & Robertson, 2007), to patients who had a laparotomy for colorectal surgery. They came to a conclusion that the change of type of analgesia from epidural to multimodal has produced comparable pain relief and also a reduction in post-operative complications, side-effects, staff intervention and hospital stay.

Early Ambulation

In a randomized controlled trial conducted by (Almeida, et al., 2017), they concluded that there is an improved functional capacity after an early post-operative mobilization in patients who had major elective abdominal surgery.

Early Nutrition

A study entitled “Impact of Nutrition on Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) in Gynecologic Oncology” conducted by (Bisch, Nelson, & Altman, 2019) has concluded that post-operative nutrition should be started immediately after surgery and can be advanced rapidly. Nutritional management should be tailored to specific patient needs and comorbidities using evidence-based decisions

whenever possible.

Processes

Pre-admission process:

Pre-admission information, education and counselling. Is paramount since it is where the patient learn the importance of each elements in ERAS protocol. From there the patient is activated and role acceptance takes place, where the patient feels confident in making decisions, actively engage, and participate in the whole process thereafter. A pamphlet called ERAS passport is given to the patient containing necessary information related to ERAS program. It is handed to the patient along with verbal education about ERAS protocol. It is known that stress and anxiety level decreases if patients and family are prepared emotionally and psychologically, setting their expectation through education with verbal and written information.

Prehabilitation. Follows wherein ERAS screening tool is followed in order to optimize the patient's health status before surgical procedure by doing the following: anemia, nutrition and physical activity screening. There are criteria for these screening that any deviation from normal levels has corresponding management action. Smoking and alcohol cessation is being emphasized to the patient to minimize pulmonary, cardiovascular and other complications.

Perioperative process:

MIS. The adoption of minimally invasive laparoscopy and robotic surgery in gynecology has led to substantial improvements in patient outcomes by decreasing intraoperative blood loss, length of stay, analgesic requirements,

return of bowel function, length of hospitalization, and return to normal daily activities.

Opioid sparing multimodal analgesia. Opioid mitigation is a corner stone in ERAS protocol as they are linked to delayed bowel movement, sedation and PONV (Post-operative Nausea and Vomiting). Utilization of multimodal non-opioid analgesia is recommended which consist of administration of two or more analgesics that act by different mechanism of pain relief. Paracetamol and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs such as acetaminophine, gabapentin and dexamethasone in combination with regional nerve blocks or wound infiltration provides comparable post-operative analgesia, and provide faster recovery.

Maintenance of blood sugar level. Diabetic and non-diabetic patient should be monitored for blood sugar level and keep it maintained between 72-200mg/dl for proper glycemic control perioperatively. Both extremes Hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia has been associated with high mortality risk and perioperative hyperglycemia on the other hand, increases the risk of developing surgical site infections.

VTE (Venous Thromboembolism) prophylaxis. Should be initiated pre-operatively and continued post-operatively. Use of stockings, pneumatic compression devices and low molecular weight heparin is highly recommended based ERAS society guidelines. It extends up to 28 days after surgery to patients who meet high risk ACCP (American College of Clinical Pharmacy) criteria.

Maintenance of Normothermia. It is vital keeping the core body temperature of the patient within or more 36 degrees pre-operatively, intra-operatively and post-operatively. Intra operative hypothermia has been linked to an increased risk of post-operative complications such as surgical site infections and cardiac events. Methods that are used to maintain normothermia includes forced air blanket devices, underbody warming mattresses, warmed intravenous fluid administration and controlled operating room temperature. Keeping the patient warm perioperatively.

Pre-operative preparation process

Optional bowel prep. Pre-operative bowel preparation is traditionally used with the aim to decrease post-operative infectious morbidity including anastomotic leak following bowel surgery. However, in established ERAS pathway, routine pre-operative bowel preparation should not be used before minimally invasive gynecologic surgery. Its use is also discouraged before open laparotomy in gynecologic surgery/gynecologic oncology.

8 hours fasting and Carbo Load. Avoiding fasting and use of pre-operative oral carbohydrates attenuate post-operative metabolic responses brought about by surgical stress. It has been shown to improve pre-operative well-being, reduce post-operative insulin resistance, decrease protein breakdown, better maintain lean body mass and muscle strength, and provide beneficial cardiac effects.

Skin preparation. Pre-operatively includes making patient do the pre-operative bathing with chlorhexidine based antimicrobial soap.

Intra-operative process

Standard anesthetic protocol. Propofol in combination with several intravenous anesthetic agents such as dexmedetomidine, ketamine, and lidocaine. Dexmedetomidine reduces opioid requirements and minimum alveolar concentration levels for inhalational anesthetics. Ketamine has potential benefits of reduced chronic post-operative pain. Intravenous lidocaine infusion in the perioperative period decreases intraoperative anesthetic requirements, lowers pain scores, reduces post-operative analgesic requirements.

Opioid sparing multi-modal analgesia. Opioid mitigation is a cornerstone in ERAS protocol as they are linked to delayed bowel movement, sedation and PONV. Utilization of multimodal non-opioid analgesia is recommended which consist of administration of two or more analgesics that act by different mechanism of pain relief. Paracetamol and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs in combination with regional nerve blocks or wound infiltration provides comparable post-operative analgesia, and provide faster recovery. Acetaminophene, Gabapentin and Dexamethasone are examples of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs that can be used as non-opioid alternatives for post-operative pain control.

Prevention of PONV. The use of propofol and avoidance of nitrous oxide reduces the risk of PONV by 25%. A combination of three anti-emetics are used as PONV prophylaxis that stands as a strong element of ERAS protocol.

Antimicrobial prophylaxis. First generation Cephalosporins is recommended prophylaxis for hysterectomy. It has a broad coverage, low cost, and low allergenic potential. Most antibiotics should be administered within 1 hour of

incision to obtain the highest drug serum levels, with weight-based dosage adjustment and redosing based on operative time and blood loss.

Maintenance of fluid balance/GDFT. GDFT (Goal Directed Fluid Therapy) in ERAS pathway is simpler to implement as compared with patients on traditional surgery because patients on an ERAS pathway are not exposed to prolonged periods of fasting, or mechanical bowel preparations. In addition, they are given carbohydrate loading solutions the night before and the morning of surgery, allowing them for better hydration and a normal intravascular volume status.

Avoidance of drains and tubes. Nasogastric tubes should be avoided after abdominal surgery. Nasogastric intubation increases the risk of post-operative pneumonia while drains may pose as transportation in introducing bacteria to travel into a surgical wound. It is concluded in one study that biofilm formation occurs within 2 hours after insertion.

Post-operative process

Prevention of paralytic ileus. Return of bowel function is influenced by some of the following factors: exposure to opioids, fluid balance, extent of peritoneal disease and complexity of surgery, receipt of transfusion, and post-operative abdomino-pelvic complications. On the other hand, early feeding, coffee consumption and gum chewing are simple interventions that can prevent paralytic ileus.

Early ambulation. Initiated within 12 hours post surgery and continued increasing in frequency with the nurse assistance until necessary. It is one of

the elements included in ERAS pathway which requires high compliance in order to achieve improved clinical outcomes and it is associated with early return of bowel function thus prevent post-operative ileus.

Early initiation of nutrition. Sips of water is initiated when patient is fully awake in PACU (Post Anesthesia Care Unit) and It advances to soft diet in the ward when tolerated. A regular diet in the first 24 hours is necessary to maintain nutritional requirement for patient to be able to regain normal function. It is also necessary to address post-operative hyper-metabolism due to stressful reaction of the body after surgery.

Removal of FC (Foley Catheter) after 24 hours/avoidance of drains and tubes. Foley catheter is removed immediately after 24 hours to avoid infection and as well as to encourage patient to ambulate to and from the toilet. NG (Naso Gastric) tube on the other hand may cause respiratory infection. Since there is existing evidence that biofilm colonization in the drain can be detected after 2 hours, there may be harm introducing a foreign body that may serve as transportation for bacteria to travel into the surgical wound. The use of drains should weigh down the risk of infection depending on the surgical procedure that necessitates drain placement.

Discharge Process

Patients managed under an ERAS pathway are discharged in an intermediate phase of recovery, with the recovery process expected to extend into the home setting. Hospital discharge is a key transition phase for patients and caregivers. It is crucial to provide tailored information, ensuring that each patient's informational needs are met, for them to successfully manage recovery at home

before hospital discharge. a. Full mobility b. Ability to tolerate oral nutrition without nausea and vomiting c. Adequate pain control with oral analgesia d. Provided written information including guide to notify surgical team, recovery advice and emergency contact information.

The conceptualization of ERAS in a Specialist Hospital in KSA

Before ERAS is implemented, patients that will undergo surgical procedures are dealt with the primary surgical team and it is usually based on their preferences. There is no protocol and or guidelines in place to be followed by everyone.

Same what happens to the floor, from the moment the patient is admitted, the nurses will carry out standard surgical preparation and follow doctor's orders for post-operative patient nursing management and interventions.

Some of the patients are not well informed about the procedure and are confused, making it hard for them to understand and fail to fully participate in the process and with other activities that are necessary for their care. They are anxious and afraid of what is going on with them making them more stressful affecting their recovery.

Until ERAS or enhanced recovery after surgery program was introduced and has proven that it bears all the evidence based elements that meet the requirements for an excellent clinical outcomes. Consequently, the following concepts are being utilized to be able to come up with the best perioperative care pathway.

Standardized practice and patient care. In implementation of ERAS, an

established protocol was designed guided by evidence conducted in other facilities in order to improve patient care. Surgeons, Anesthesiologists, Nurses, and Allied health follow one path into collaboration to achieve one common goal - early recovery. In unison, multi-disciplinary health care members involved in the care of the patient work together effectively. The clinical practice guidelines that is formulated serves as the backbone of ERAS making clinical language and practice among clinical staff comprehensive and reliable.

Program/Protocol formulation. As the ERAS program is incorporated to the clinical practice, patients that are enrolled to this has the most of the benefit. As they are well informed and educated, it lessen their anxiety and fear of the unknown brought about by the impending surgical procedure. As the paramount goal of the program is patient and family education, it is the most important element of the protocol that the patient and family has to receive. It gives them knowledge and confidence to take responsibility and ownership of their own health care. Hence, their full participation and active involvement result to optimum and quality surgical outcome.

Related Statistics

Figure one and two presents the data before and after ERAS implementation in a Specialist hospital in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Figure 1. Pre ERAS and post ERAS average LOS

Figure 2. Pre ERAS and post ERAS post operative complication rate

		Post-op Complications	
		0%	0%
		0%	5%
		0%	0%
		Paralytic Ileus	SSI in 30 Days
■ Pre ERAS		0%	5%
■ Post ERAS		0%	0%

Figure 1 & 2 shows the data of Length of stay and post-operative complications pre ERAS and post ERAS implementation in the specialist hospital in KSA. Retrospective data acquired through electronic data record conducted by Dr. Fatimah Danyan prior pilot implementation of ERAS among two surgical specialties.

Figure 1 shows overall average length of stay of patients pre ERAS and post ERAS. Pre ERAS (N=21) patients has stayed in the hospital for 4.1 days. After ERAS implementation, patients (N=8) stayed in the hospital only for 3.2 days.

Figure 2 shows post operative complication rate data. Surgical site infection rate is 5% pre-eras. After ERAS implementation, there were no post-operative complications noted.

Figure 3. Over all complications

“Enhanced recovery after surgery protocol versus conventional perioperative care in colorectal surgery. A single center cohort study” (Javier et al., 2018), graph presented in the study showed improvement in the number of post operative complications after ERAS implementation.

Synthesis

A paradigm shift in perioperative care that has delivered substantial improvement in clinical outcomes. The already existing knowledge and practice on surgical patient care journey has changed and developed to achieve the highest standard utilizing the best available evidence based literature.

The standardized processes that is presented in implementation of ERAS will give direction and uniformity of care to all healthcare providers. Thus, maintain stability on their work process and achieve the highest and excellent outcome surgical patients in the Specialist hospital in KSA.

Theoretical Framework

In nursing care perspective, the care that is delivered by the nurse basing

on the established ERAS protocol is aligned with three independent but interconnected circles **care, cure, core** theory by Lydia Hall also known as “the Three Cs of Lydia Hall”. These three important element works together in the health care delivery of the patient as a whole.

The **care** circle which includes comfort measures, patient instruction, and helping the patient meet his/her needs including the pre-determined actions in the protocol as the goal of the nursing role. Nursing care is delivered with nurturing nature as of the mother during the period of recovery.

The **cure** circle is where multidisciplinary team and allied health is involved in collaboration of patient care throughout the recovery period. Specialized health services work hand in hand with the nurse in meeting the need of the patient.

The **core** is where the patient claimed ownership of their own health care journey, setting their own goals in accordance to their feelings and values.

This theoretical framework supports the concept of ERAS program and the individual role of each member involved in the process of patient’s surgical journey. Each health care member has important function to perform that contributes to patient enhanced recovery.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 4. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework (figure 2) is presented in two boxes. with line and arrow head from the first box pointed to the second box. The first box with listed influencing factors as the independent variables and the other box with listed length of stay and post-operative complication which includes PONV- post-operative nausea and vomiting, SSI-surgical site infection and OPI- obstructive paralytic ileus as the dependent variables.

Age, type of surgery, pre-operative fasting and carbo loading, type of analgesia, early ambulation and early nutrition are factors that affects hospital length of stay and post-operative complications.

The study revealed upon data analysis and statistical tests applied, that the list of influencing factors definitely affects the outcome of post-operative patients under ERAS protocol.

Operational Definition

Age - Is the variable in the study wherein division of participants by age was distributed from ranges 18-35 as young adult group, 36-55 middle age group

and 56 and above belongs to older adult group.

Type of Surgery - Is the variable in the study which means mode of surgery between Open abdominal surgery and laparoscopic/Robotic or minimally invasive surgery.

Pre-operative fasting and carbohydrate loading - This is the variable in the study wherein pre-operative fasting is mitigated by delivering carbohydrate loading - in a form of a drink given to the patient at midnight and two hours before surgery.

Type of analgesia - This is the variable in the study wherein modalities of pain management is identified from (PCA) patient controlled analgesia, (PCEA) patient controlled epidural analgesia and multi-modal opioid sparing analgesia.

Early ambulation - The variable in the study wherein within six hours after surgery, the patient will get out of bed and ambulate with the nurse assistance.

Early nutrition - The variable in the study wherein the patients will take sips or drink up to a glass of water as soon as completely awake from anaesthesia.

Length of stay (LOS) - The dependent variable in the study which may be longer or shorter depending on how meticulous the independent variables are implemented.

Post-operative complication - The dependent variable that incidence rely on how the perioperative processes took place. As an outcome wherein contributed with variety of elements including the influencing factors listed.

Post-operative nausea and vomiting (PONV) - The dependent variable in the

study, a type of post-operative complication that is observed among the participants after surgery.

Surgical Site Infection (SSI) - Another dependent variable under post-operative complications that is observed among post-operative surgical patients.

Obstructive Paralytic Ileus (OPI) - One of the post-operative complication that is also monitored among post-operative surgical patients especially those who have undergone abdominal operations.

Hypothesis

H1: There is a direct correlation between influencing factors, post-operative complications and Length of stay among Gyne-oncology surgery patients under ERAS protocol in a specialist hospital in KSA.

H0: There is no significant relationship between the influencing factors, post-operative complication and Length of stay among Gyne-oncology surgery patients under ERAS protocol in a specialist hospital in KSA.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This is a study of relationship between the influencing factors and length of stay, wherein a descriptive correlational design was used. It is where data collected from patients enrolled in ERAS program who are automatically qualified to be included to participate in the study. An adult female patient from aged 18 years and above, on elective admission for minimally invasive or open abdominal surgical procedure. Patients were evaluated on a daily basis taking extra attention to specific influencing factors, observed for signs of postoperative complications, and determine the hospital length of stay.

Descriptive correlational design: A study wherein the variables are described and the occurrence of relationship among them. In this study, the list of influencing factors as age, type of surgery, pre-operative fasting and carbohydrate loading, type of analgesia, early mobilization and early nutrition will be individually described and their relationship to length of stay and post-operative complication.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was used to gather data from the target population which is the Gyne-oncology surgery patients enrolled in ERAS program. As soon as approval was given from IRB, gathering of samples started at the end of June 2020 until middle of December 2020 to complete 60 patients for the study. Since not all gyne-oncology surgery booked for procedure is qualified to participate, it took 6 months to complete 60 samples.

As per inclusion criteria, sixty (60) qualified gyne-oncology surgery patients that were enrolled in ERAS program was included. Patients that are eighteen years and older, female, psychologically sound, booked for elective surgery, is aware of the program and is willing to participate throughout the whole process.

Excluding patients that are mentally challenged, local surgical procedures and non-abdominal operations.

Setting

The study was conducted in a specialist hospital located in the Eastern part of Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The facility provides accurate and sophisticated medical services to the eastern region population with many specialties and one of these is Gyne-oncology surgery.

This 633-bedded hospital is known to be one of the largest and high profile Health Institution in the Eastern Region and the entire GCC countries, and is reckoned to be one of the world's first class specialized Hospital.

Aside from experienced health care providers that are qualified to render services, It is pertinent to conduct a study where the facility is adept with the most recent and technologically advanced medical instruments from state of the art digital operating theater, and robotic surgical machine. Furthermore, the availability of allied health services such as nutrition, physiotherapy and other specialties needed is in place to support and complete the requirement in the implementation of ERAS program.

Data Collection

As participants are identified based on eligibility criteria, data were

collected in observational method from 60 patients. Necessary data collection tools are made for appropriate data collection process. Patient profile were collected using patient profile sheet, while improvement evaluative table was used to record observed improvement status of the patient.

Data were recorded in a systematic way using ERAS data collection template that is designed to hold as much of many important information which contains preparation or pre admission, pre operative, intra operative, post operative , outcomes and most importantly the variables needed for this study which is length of hospital stay and post-operative complication rate.

The data collected from daily follow up of patient progress (from admission to discharge), random questions, nursing and physician documentation updates, lab work ups and investigations, daily patient progress record, and physician order sheet, were included and recorded accordingly in ERAS data collection sheet for appropriate analysis.

Research Instruments

Instruments that are utilized in this study includes ERAS data collection template, improvement status table which is used to record observation of frequency of ambulation, level of pain, and transition of diet. ERAS data spreadsheet, is where data collected was arranged and collated.

Paralytic Ileus assessment form was used to detect symptoms of post-operative paralytic ileus the patient has manifested.

Surgical site assessment form was prepared to be utilized to record symptoms of post-operative surgical site infection.

Evaluative indicators of improvement status includes data of average number of patients that had manifested PONV 24 hours and after 24 hours post operatively. Average number of patients that have started to mobilize 6 hours after surgery and ambulate around the unit 24 hours after surgery. Also includes average number of days of bowel return and diet progress of the patient.

Recovery rate table was used to help determine the influence of age, type of surgery, fasting and carbohydrate loading, type of analgesia, early ambulation and early nutrition to the rate of recovery.

Figure 5. Surgical site infection and Paralytic Ileus Assessment Tool

<p style="text-align: center;">ENHANCED RECOVERY AFTER SURGERY SURGICAL SITE ASSESSMENT FORM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> FEVER/CHILLS<input type="checkbox"/> SURGICAL SITE HOT TO TOUCH<input type="checkbox"/> REDNESS<input type="checkbox"/> PAIN OR SORE TO TOUCH<input type="checkbox"/> PUS OR DRAINAGE<input type="checkbox"/> BAD SMELL COMING FROM THE WOUND <hr/> <p style="text-align: center;">ENHANCED RECOVERY AFTER SURGERY PARALYTIC ILEUS ASSESSMENT FORM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="checkbox"/> DECREASED/ABSENT BOWEL SOUNDS<input type="checkbox"/> ABDOMINAL DISTENTION<input type="checkbox"/> ABDOMINAL PAIN<input type="checkbox"/> (X-RAY REPORT) MULTIPLE AIR-FLUID LEVELS IN THE ABDOMEN

Figure 6. ERAS data collection sheet

ERAS DATA COLLECTION TEMPLATE

ADMISSION:		HEIGHT:		ANEMIA SCREENING:	
SURGERY:		WEIGHT:		<input type="checkbox"/> IV IRON	
DISCHARGE:		BMI:		<input type="checkbox"/> ORAL IRON	
LOS:				<input type="checkbox"/> NUTRITIONAL SCREENING	
NAME OF SURGERY:				<input type="checkbox"/> PHYSICAL ACTIVITY	
				ERAS PASSPORT:	
SURGEON:				<input type="checkbox"/> PRE ADMISSION	<input type="checkbox"/> PRE SURGERY
ANESTHESIOLOGIST:				HEMOGLOBIN:	
ANESTHESIA:	START		END		ON SCREENING:
SURGERY:	START		END		PRE OP:
TEMPERATURE MAINTAINED:				POST OP:	
				CREATININE:	
<input type="checkbox"/> RBS	<input type="checkbox"/> PRE OP WARMING			PRE OP	
<input type="checkbox"/> LIDOCAINE	<input type="checkbox"/> V PCA/ <input type="checkbox"/> PCEA			POST OP	
<input type="checkbox"/> HEPARIN					
<input type="checkbox"/> PROPHYLAXIS ANTIBIOTICS				PRE OP:	
ANTIEMETICS:				<input type="checkbox"/> BOWEL PREP	
				<input type="checkbox"/> CARBO LOAD	
<input type="checkbox"/> MAGNESIUM BOLUS				<input type="checkbox"/> GABAPENTIN ORDERED	
<input type="checkbox"/> EPIDURAL				<input type="checkbox"/> ANTISEPTIC	
<input type="checkbox"/> TAP BLOCK				SHOWER/MOUTHWASH	
<input type="checkbox"/> PARACETAMOL INTRA OP					
FLUID MANAGEMENT :				POST OP:	
OPIOID INTRA OP:				<input type="checkbox"/> INCENTIVE SPIROMETER	
				6 HOURS POST OP:	
<input type="checkbox"/> FOLEY CATH REMOVED IN 24H:				<input type="checkbox"/> OUT OF BED	
<input type="checkbox"/> PONV 24H/ <input type="checkbox"/> AFTER 24H				PAIN SCORE	
RETURN OF BOWEL:				DIET	
OPIOID POST OP:				24 HOURS POST OP:	
ANTIEMETIC POST OP:				<input type="checkbox"/> OUT OF BED	
<input type="checkbox"/> PARACETAMOL POST OP				PAIN SCORE	
				DIET	

Interpretation of data by observation will go by scoring. Elements in the improvement indicators has corresponding score when met. Summing up the total score will tell the improvement status of the patient.

Table 1.

Improvement progress evaluation table

IMPROVEMENT EVALUATIVE INDICATORS	PONV	DIET PROGRESS	AMBULATION	BOWEL RETURN
DAY 0 POST-OP SCORE(3)	NO NAUSEA AND VOMITING	CLEAR LIQUID TO FULL LIQUID	12 HOURS POST OP OUT OF BED AND SIT ON A CHAIR 2 HOURS PER DAY	
DAY 1-2 POST-OP SCORE (4)	NO NAUSEA AND VOMITING	SOFT TO REGULAR DIET	24 HOURS POST OP OUT OF BED WALK AROUND THE UNIT 6X PER DAY	AUDIBLE BOWEL SOUNDS
Day 3 to DISCHARGE SCORE (4)	NO NAUSEA AND VOMITING	FULL DIET	FULLY AMBULATORY WITHOUT ASSISTANCE	AUDIBLE BOWEL SOUNDS FLATUS/BOWEL MOVEMENT
TOTAL SCORE				

SCORING:

10-11 - Fully Improved, 6-10 - Partially Improved, 6 And below – Slight Improvement

Interpretation of data by observation will go by scoring. Elements in the improvement indicators has corresponding score when met. Summing up the total score will tell the improvement status of the patient.

Table 2.

Patient profile sheet

PATIENT PROFILE:	AGE	STATUS	NATIONALITY
PATIENT A			
PATIENT B			
PATIENT C			

Age, status and nationality were included in the patient profile data collection.

Table 3.

Influencing factors and recovery rate table

VARIABLES	DATE OF ADMISSION TO DISCHARGE	AGE	TYPE OF SURGERY (MIS/OPEN)	PRE OPERATIVE FASTING AND CARBO LOADING	TYPE OF ANALGESIA	EARLY AMBULATION	EARLY NUTRITION
PATIENT A							
PATIENT B							
PATIENT C							
PATIENT D							
PATIENT E							

A tool to be used in recording variables that may affect patients recovery progress. This table will help analyse the data on how the variables included: age, type of surgery, pre-operative fasting and carbo loading, type of analgesia, early ambulation and early nutrition affects the recovery rate or length of hospital stay of the participants.

Figure 5. Procedure flow chart

When the need to establish how the influencing factors affects the result of ERAS program implementation on Gyne-oncology surgery patients was identified, proposal of the study was initiated. The aim is to determine the patient demographics, the average length of stay, the incidence of post-operative complications, and the relationship among these variables.

It was then approved which proceeded to planning and preparation of necessary documents and actions to pursue the research. It has started with identifying qualified patients to participate in the study. Some data were collected through direct observation, random interview, review of nursing/physician documentation, and lab investigations. Then, the data collected was encoded in ERAS data collection template (hard copy form) and was transferred to ERAS data spreadsheet (excel sheet). Patient profiling has begun by recording the participants profile in the patient profile sheet. Variables were recorded in the influencing factors and recovery rate table to clearly organize the data. Then statistical analysis was applied to come up with reliable result. Subsequently, comprehension of the result was done to come up with conclusion. Then finally reporting of the result has carried through.

Plan for Data Analysis

Table 4.

Data analysis table plan

Specific variable	Instruments	Variables used	Level of measurement	Specific stat test
Length of stay	Data collection template	Age	Ordinal	Spearman's rho, Frequency, Average percentage Chi-square,
	Recovery rate table	Type of surgery	Nominal	

		Pre-op fasting and Carbohydrate Loading	Nominal	Frequency, Average Percentage
		Type of analgesia		Chi-square, Frequency, Average Percentage
		Early Ambulation	Nominal	Percentage
		Early Nutrition	Nominal	Chi-square, Frequency, Average Percentage
			Nominal	Chi-square, Average Percentage, frequency, Chi-square, Average percentage, frequency
Paralytic Ileus (Post-operative complication)	Paralytic Ileus assessment form	Flatus Bowel sounds Bowel movement	Nominal	Frequency, average percentage
Surgical Site Infection (Post-operative complication)	Surgical Site Infection assessment form	Fever Pain Swelling	Nominal	Frequency, average percentage
PONV (post-operative nausea and vomiting - post operative complication)	ERAS data collection form Recovery status table	Nausea and vomiting 24 hours after surgery Nausea and vomiting after 24hours after surgery	Nominal	Frequency, average percentage, chi square

Looking at table 4, data analysis table plan displays the specific variables in the study and how they were analyzed using different testing tools. Chi-square was used to analyze variables with nominal level of measurement and Spearman's rho was used in variable with ordinal level of measurement. Average percentage and frequency were also determined to help analyze the data.

For the post-operative complication specific to PONV, frequency and average were calculated and chi-square was also used in order to determine its correlation to length of stay.

Data Management

Data that collected was stored in a personal laptop secured with password accessible only by the principal investigator. The data will be kept for at least 5 years after the research study before being destroyed.

Ethical Considerations

Approval from Institutional Review Board was obtained, collection of data started as soon as decision letter was received. Recommended policies and protocol as per IRB manual was followed and that any changes in the protocol was submitted for amendment approval. The study was performed in accordance with the following basic ethical considerations.

Informed Consent. Information regarding the purpose of the study, how the findings will be used, if there are any potential adverse impacts of their participation and who will have access to the findings will be given to the participants. They should be made aware of these before acquiring the consent.

In this study, IRB advised that invitation to participate instead of consent will be given to the participants. However, after them seeing that all data that will be collected is part of standard of care, IRB advised that consent or invitation is not necessary.

Voluntary Participation. The participants had free will to participate, not influenced by intimidation or by force. They have the right to choose not to

continue or withdraw from participation without pressure and required explanation.

Do no Harm. The participants are protected from any form of physiological, emotional and spiritual harm throughout the research study.

Confidentiality. The name or other identifying information are not included in any reports or published documents.

Anonymity. Identity of every participants in the study are protected including to the member of the research team.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This part of the paper presents, analyze, interpret and explains the findings, in conformity with the objectives of the study.

The study was initiated to ascertain the average length of stay and incidence of post-operative complications. Correlation between this two variables was also determined as well as the effects of Influencing variables: Age, type of surgery, pre-operative fasting and carbo loading, type of analgesia, early mobilization and early nutrition among surgical patients of the specialist hospital in KSA.

After data were analyzed, the outcome are the following as shown.

Demographic Profile of the respondents

Table 5.

Socio-Demographic profile

Demographic Profile	Frequency (N=60)	Percentage
	Age range	
18-35	N=11	18.3%
36-55	N=21	35%
56-older	N=28	46.6%
	Status	
Single	N=8	13.3%
Married	N=32	53%
Widowed	N=3	5%
Divorced	N=1	1.6%
(*)	N=16	26.7%
	Nationality	
Saudi	N=53	88%
Filipino	N=4	6.7%
Yemeni	N=2	3.3%
Pakistani	N=1	1.6%

(*) means no information

The total number of participants were divided in three age groups, young adult group is (n=11) 18% ages from 18-35. The middle age group is ranging

from 36-55 with (n=21) 35%, and the older adult age is group ranging from 56-older of (n=28) 46.4%.

Majority of the participants (N=32) 53% are married, (N=8) 13.3% are single, (n=3) 5% are widowed, (N=1) 1.6% divorced, and (N=16) 26.7% have not revealed their civil status.

Four nationalities are identified among the participants, mostly constitute of Saudi national (N=53) 88%, Filipino (N=4) 6.7%, Yemeni (N=3.3%), and Pakistani (N=1) 1.6%, coming from different regions within and outside of Eastern province.

Influencing Factors

Table 6.

Frequency and percentage of the influencing factors

Variables	Frequency (N-60)	Percentage
AGE RANGE		
18-35 Young Adult	11	18 %
36-55 Middle Age	21	32 %
56-Older Older Adult	28	46.6 %
TYPE OF SURGERY		
OPEN Surgery	47	33%
MIS	13	27%
PRE-OP FASTING AND CARBOHYDRATE TREATMENT		
YES	50	83.3%
NO	10	16.6%
TYPE OF ANALGESIA		
PCA	27	45%

PCEA	18	30%
Multi modal (Opioid sparing)	15	25%
EARLY AMBULATION		
YES	46	76.6%
NO	14	23.3%
EARLY NUTRITION		
YES	58	96.6%
NO	2	3.3%

Table 7.

Frequency and average length of stay of the influencing factors

Variables	Frequency (N-60)	Average Length of stay
AGE RANGE		
18-35 Young Adult	11	3.3 Days
19 y	1	1 Day
19 y	1	1 Day
26 y	1	5 Days
28 y	1	2 Days
32 y	1	5 Days
32 y	1	4 Days
33 y	1	3 Days
33 y	1	2 Days
34 y	1	5 Days
34 y	1	4 Days
35 y	1	4 Days
36-55 Middle Age	21	3 Days
36 y	1	2 Days
37 y	1	2 Days
39 y	1	1 Day
39 y	1	1 Day
40 y	1	2 days
40 y	1	4 days
40 y	1	3 Days
42 y	1	3 Days
44 y	1	4 Days
47 y	1	2 Days

47 y	1	5 Days
48 y	1	4 Days
49 y	1	1 Day
49 y	1	4 Days
49 y	1	2 Days
49 y	1	4 Days
51 y	1	3 Days
51 y	1	4 Days
51 y	1	8 Days
53 y	1	2 Days
55 y	1	4 Days

56-Older Older Adult	28	3 Days
-----------------------------	-----------	---------------

56 y	1	2 Days
57 y	1	2 Days
57 y	1	3 Days
58 y	1	2 Days
60 y	1	1 Day
60 y	1	3 Days
60 y	1	4 Days
61 y	1	3 Days
61 y	1	1 Day
61 y	1	2 Days
61 y	1	4 Days
62 y	1	4 Days
62 y	1	4 Days
63 y	1	1 Day
63 y	1	4 Days
64 y	1	3 Days
65 y	1	5 Days
65 y	1	4 Days
65 y	1	3 Days
65 y	1	3 Days
66 y	1	5 Days
66 y	1	3 Days
69 y	1	6 Days
70 y	1	3 Days
72 y	1	4 Days
73 y	1	3 Days
79 y	1	1 Day
79 y	1	1 Day

TYPE OF SURGERY

OPEN Surgery	47	3.5 Days
MIS	13	1.7 Days
PRE-OP FASTING AND CARBOHYDRATE TREATMENT		
YES	50	2.9 Days
NO	10	3.7 Days

TYPE OF ANALGESIA

PCA	27	3 Days
PCEA	18	4 Days
Multi modal (Opioid sparing)	15	2 Days

EARLY AMBULATION

YES	46	2.8 Days
NO	14	4 Days

EARLY NUTRITION

YES	58	3 Days
NO	2	3.5 Days

Age

Looking at the data in table 9, the analysis resulted to hospital length of stay in middle age group (N=21) 32% and older age group (N=28) 46.6% being the same with average of 3 days. While among younger adult age group (N=11) 18%, there is a very slight increase in the average length of hospital stay of 3.3 days. Similar findings in the study conducted by (Forsmo, Erichsen, & Rasdal, 2017) which concluded that “Elderly patients adhered to and benefited from an ERAS program, similar to their younger counterparts”, and resulted to insignificant total post-operative hospital stay between age groups participating in ERAS program.

Type of surgery

Analyzing data with the type of surgery in comparison between Open and MIS (minimally invasive surgery), the result showed that MIS (N=13) has

an average of 1.7 days of hospital stay while patients who have undergone Open surgery (N=47) has stayed in the hospital for an average of 3.5 days. This result supports the strong recommendation of erassociety.org guidelines of minimally invasive/robotic surgery, since this method decrease intraoperative blood loss, analgesic requirements, return of bowel function, length of hospitalization, and return to normal daily activities.

Pre-operative fasting and carbohydrate treatment

Analysis of the data showed that participants who received carbohydrate treatment prior surgery (N=50) 83.3% has stayed in the hospital for 2.9 days, while participants who did not receive carbohydrate treatment (N=10) 16.6% has stayed longer in the hospital (3.7 days). Carbohydrate loading is given to patients 12 midnight, then 6am day of operation, and they are allowed fluid intake up to 2 hours before surgery. Instead of fasting, they are allowed clear liquid diet up to 2 hours before surgery. It is concluded in the study of (Weledji, et al., 2017) entitled “The effects of preoperative carbohydrate loading on the metabolic response to surgery in a low resource setting” that “Preoperative CHO loading is effective and safe in reducing post-operative hyperglycaemia and infection in open general surgery even in a low resource setting”.

Type of analgesia: Multi-modal Opioid sparing analgesia

In the type of analgesia, the data showed that (N=27) 45% of the participants received (PCA) patient controlled analgesia who stayed in the hospital for 3 days, (N=18) 30% received (PCEA) patient controlled epidural analgesia who stayed for 4 days and (N=15) 25% had multimodal opioid sparing analgesia who had stayed for only 2 days. Both PCA and PCEA pain

management include the use of opioids while multimodal opioid sparing pain management utilizes combination of pain medications with different mechanisms of action. As explained in the study of (Charipova, Gress, Urits, Viswanath, & Kaye, 2020) that ERAS is minimizing, and ultimately eliminating, use of opioids. The use of multimodal analgesia with reliance on opioids only for rescue and short acting opioids if in case it has to be used.

Early ambulation

The data showed that those who ambulated early (N=46) 76.6% has recovered faster and was discharged after 2.8 days. While participants who were not able to ambulate early, has stayed in the hospital for 4 days. This only means that the study conducted by (Grass, et al., 2018) support this result, since their study revealed a significant association between bed rest and post-operative complications. The result also convey a significant correlation of early ambulation with post-operative outcomes.

Early nutrition

It is shown in the table that participants who have resumed nutrition earlier (N=58) 96.6% had stayed in the hospital for 3 days, while those who are delayed (N=2) 3.3% stayed for 3.5 days. As discussed in the study of (Kim, et al., 2018) that exacerbation of catabolism is brought about by fasting. However, early initiation of nutrition post-operatively can improve recovery of patients. Thus, decreasing length of stay and risk of post-operative complications.

POST-OPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS

Table 8.

Frequency and percentage of post-operative complications

Variables	Frequency (N-60)	Percentage
POST OPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS		
Total PONV	15	25%
Without PONV	45	75%
Paralytic ileus	0	0
Surgical site infection	0	0

Table 9.

Frequency and Length of Stay of Post-operative complications

Variables	Frequency (N-60)	Average Length of stay
POST OPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS		
Total PONV	15	3.8 Days
Without PONV	45	2.9 Days
Paralytic ileus	0	0
Surgical site infection	0	0

Post operative nausea and vomiting (PONV)

The findings of the study shows that PONV is the only post-operative complications that had manifested in total of 25% of patients after surgery. 8.3% (N-5) of the participants has displayed it within 24 hours after surgery, while 17% (N-10) has it after 24 hours post-operatively.

Looking at the table 11, as expected, the total average LOS of stay of affected participants is 3.8 days, which appeared to be higher compared to those without PONV participants, which stayed in the hospital for only 2.9 days.

Paralytic Ileus

No findings of other possible post operative complications such as paralytic ileus, and surgical site infection in the data collected. Paralytic ileus is identified as one of post operative complications that influence length of stay. Preoperative fasting and bowel preparation, analgesic and anesthetic techniques, perioperative fluid management, use of nasogastric tube, and postoperative diet restrictions are contributors to ileus.

Surgical Site Infection

Based on baseline data of the specialist hospital, surgical site infection was 5% pre ERAS and 0% after ERAS pilot implementation. In this study, no participant has experienced this specific post-operative complication. It is indicative that the surgical site infection bundle in place is effective and efficient and has worked well with other elements of ERAS protocol.

Improvement Status

Table 10 shows the percentage of full and partial improvement with the variables that influence the improvement status of the participants. Presented in Chapter 3 table 3, the improvement evaluative indicators with scoring was used to come up with data to support whether the participants has recovered and has improved fully or improved partially within day 3 up to discharge from the hospital.

Table 10.

Level of improvement percentage table

Variables	Fully improved	Partially improved
AGE RANGE		
18-35 Young Adult	72 %	28 %
36-55 Middle Age	76 %	24 %
56-Older Older Adult	62 %	38 %
TYPE OF SURGERY		
OPEN Surgery	62%	28%
MIS	100%	0%
Pre-operative fasting and carbo loading		
YES	72%	28%
NO	60%	40%
Early mobilization		
YES	78.2%	21.7%
NO	42.8%	57.1%
Early Nutrition		
YES	74.5%	14.5%
NO	20%	80%
TYPE OF ANALGESIA		
PCA	77.7%	22.2%
PCEA	44.4%	55.5%
Multi modal	86.6%	13.3%

Age

Looking at the data presented in table 10, age range was shown with

corresponding percentage of full improvement and partial improvement. Data shows that young adult (72%) and middle age group (76%) have almost the same percentage of full improvement. While older adult age group (62%) is lower. As concluded in the study conducted by (Massarweh, Legner, & Symons, 2009) that “older adults may have greater difficulty recovering from surgery because of decreased physiologic reserve,³⁻⁵ but many case series have reported acceptable rates of adverse outcomes after a variety of abdominal surgical procedures.”

Type of Surgery

As shown in table 10, patients who went for minimally invasive surgery have all recovered fully (100%). While 62% have fully recovered from those who went for open abdominal surgery. As discussed in the study of (Korsholm, et al., 2017) that several cancer centers worldwide, have shifted towards the use of minimally invasive surgical techniques as adaptation of paradigm shift in healthcare, especially on the use of robotic-assisted laparoscopy (e.g. for localized endometrial and cervical cancer). Consecutively, several studies have confirmed that minimally invasive surgery is very safe with low risk of adverse events and quality oncologic outcomes.

Pre-operative fasting and carbo loading

As data showed in table 10, a total of 72% of participants who have carbo loading has fully improved, while 60% of those who did not receive carbo load. In conclusion of the study conducted by (Kratzing, 2011) entitled “Pre-operative nutrition and carbohydrate loading”, post-operative outcomes are improved when nutritional state of severely malnourished patients is enhanced. Reduced surgical induced stress, attenuating insulin resistance, preserving

muscle function and improving patient comfort is achieved by reducing pre-operative fasting periods and increasing carbohydrate loading.

Early nutrition

As appeared in table 10, 74.5% of patients who have tolerated early nutrition has fully improved and only 20% from those who did not. The findings of the study conducted by (Khan & Latifi, 2019) asserts that European Society for Parenteral and Enteral Nutrition guidelines recommends early nutrition to improve outcomes after surgery and increase the rate of recovery. They further affirm that nutritional support should be personalized, and disease process-based.

Early ambulation

Table 8 showed data with 74.5% full improvement in patients who ambulated early and 20% of those who did not after surgery. As discussed in the study conducted by (Sthethen, et al., 2018) failure to ambulate of patients after surgery, increase length of stay of MIS patients 2.3 days and 3.1 days in Open surgery patients. They further assert in their findings that ambulating greater distance decrease the length of stay in both and MIS and Open surgery cohorts.

Type of post-operative analgesia

Type of analgesia affects improvement of the participants. As table 10 shows that 77.7% of patients that had PCA has full improved, 44.4% fully recovered with PCEA and 86.6% with multimodal analgesia. In the summary of the study entitled "Multimodal Analgesia, Current Concepts, and Acute Pain Considerations", conducted by (Helander, et al., 2017), they assert that overall, a multimodal analgesic approach should be used when treating postoperative pain,

as it can potentially reduce side effects and provide the benefit of treating pain through different cellular pathways.

Table 11.

Post-operative complication and level of improvement percentage

Variables	Fully improved	Partially improved
POST OPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS		
Post operative nausea and vomiting (PONV)	31.5%	68.5%
Paralytic ileus	0	0
Surgical site infection	0	0
No PONV	80%	20%

Table 11 shows data of level of improvement of patients with and without PONV. 80% of the participants without PONV has fully improved, while only 63% has fully improved in those with PONV. As discussed in the study of (Johns, Gerling, & Jong, 2017) that Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) is common in all age groups and can have a significant negative impact on patient comfort and recovery after surgery. On the other hand, in the discussion of the study conducted by (Myles & Wengritzky, 2012), they found that around 1:5 patients with PONV have clinical features consistent with distress and physical limitations affecting their recovery after surgery. It includes inability to tolerate oral fluids and food, impaired mobilization, and an overall poorer quality of recovery.

Table 12.

Results of data statistical analysis

Factors	Calculator	Score	P-Value
Age	Spearman's rho	rs = 0.04836	P-Value (2-tailed) = 0.71367
Type of surgery	Chi ²	value=54.675	p-value= < .00001
Pre-op fasting and Carbohydrate loading	Chi ²	value = 5.455	p-value = .01952
Type of Analgesia	Chi ²	value = 50.925	p-value = < .00001
Early ambulation	Chi ²	value = 17.673	p-value = .00003
Early Nutrition	Chi ²	value = ∞	p-value = < .00001
PONV	Chi ²	value =3	p-value = .08326

Table 11 shows the result of data analysis on the influencing factors in the study. Using Spearman's rho correlation data analysis, age is analysed how it is correlated to length of stay. Results showed (rs = 0.04836, p (2-tailed) = 0.71367), which means that by normal standards, the association between the two variables would not be considered statistically significant. On the other hand, according to the study conducted by Melissa Mattison, MD entitled "Hospital management of older adults", Older adults have greater vulnerability to acute stress than younger individuals due to age-related diminution of physiologic reserves (Mattison, 2021), but in ERAS protocol, they can recuperate with the same phase with other age groups. The reason why all age group have similar

average length of hospital stay. Therefore, statistical analysis result of correlation between age and length of stay failed to reject the null hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between influencing factors (age) and Length of stay.

Chi-square test applied to analyse data in the type of surgery, with expectations (Open=20 and MIS=40) and defaults to ($p \leq 0.05$) has resulted to significant value (Chi² value = 54.675 and $p\text{-value} < .00001$) which means that the alternative hypothesis is true, and that there is a direct correlation between influencing factors (type of surgery) and length of stay.

With chi-square test used to analyse data in pre-op fasting and carbohydrate loading, using default significance value of ($p \leq 0.05$) and expected value (Yes=55 and No=5) showed results (Chi² value= 5.455) and ($p\text{-value} = .01952$), which means that the result is significant at $p \leq .05$. Thus, means that the result supports the alternative hypothesis of the study: There is a direct correlation between influencing factors (Pre-operative fasting and carbo loading) and length of stay.

Analyzing data using chi square test in type of analgesia, with expectations (PCEA=10, PCA=10, and Multimodal analgesia=40) and with default significance level ($p \leq 0.05$) resulted to (Chi² value= 50.925) and ($p\text{-value} < .00001$), which means that type of analgesia is significant and supports the hypothesis of the study that there is a correlation between influencing factors (type of analgesia) and length of stay.

Chi-square test analysis was done in the data of early ambulation using default significance level of ($p \leq 0.05$) and expectations (Yes=55, No=5) resulted to (Chi² value = 17.673 and $p\text{-value} = .00003$). Which means, that early

ambulation is significant and supports the alternative hypothesis that there is a direct correlation between influencing factors (early ambulation) and hospital length of stay.

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The study was conducted to determine and ascertain relationship between the influencing factors, post-operative complication and length of stay of Gynecology surgery patients under ERAS protocol in a specialist hospital in KSA.

The participants are all female from ages 18 to 80 years old (N=60), 88% (N=53) are Saudi nationals and the rest are Filipino (N=4), Yemeni (N=2) and Pakistani (N=1). Majority are married composed of (N=32) 56%, quite many (N=16) 26.7% did not provide their status and the remaining are widowed (N=3), divorced (N=1) and single (N=16). Larger part of the total number of participants (N=45) 61.5% came from different areas within Eastern Region and (N=13) 21.6% did not provide their address, while only (N=2) 3.2% came from another Region in KSA.

The Length of stay were measured categorized among influencing factors: age, type of surgery, pre-operative fasting and carbo loading, type of analgesia, early ambulation, and early nutrition. Analysing data with grouping the participants by age apparently shows that in ERAS protocol, all age group has the same length of stay. The participants that had undergone minimally invasive surgery showed significant shorter hospital length of stay of 1.7 days and 100% full improvement. In ERAS protocol, minimally invasive surgery is recommended. As stated in the study of John L. Ochsner, MD entitled "Minimally Invasive Surgical Procedures" that MIS is generally the use of ports and/or small incisions that reduces pain and substantially reduces postoperative care and cost

(Ochsner, 2000). Pre-operative fasting and carbo-loading has also showed significant outcomes when patients with carbohydrate load stayed in the hospital for 2.9 days and 3.7 days for those who did not have. Fasting is known to cause catabolic stress which leads to consistently high blood sugar level causing insulin resistance. Therefore, allowing patients on clear liquids and carbohydrate load delivered two hours before surgery, results to lesser incidence of post-operative complication and shorter hospital stay. Multimodal analgesia applied to patients post-operatively resulted to 2 days length of hospital stay in comparison to patients who have PCA and PCEA who stayed longer. Since postoperative pain is a complex and multifactorial symptom, it requires a varied approach using a different types of pain management modalities to achieve an optimal outcome post operatively. With early mobilization, patients who were able to tolerate it stayed in the hospital for 2.8 days, while four days to those who were not able to ambulate early. A clear indicative that in this study, early mobilization promotes early restoration of physical function, lower the risk of post-operative complications and shorten hospital length of stay. Early nutrition proved to deliver positive effect on post-operative patients. As early as soon the patient is fully awake from anaesthesia, patient is allowed to take from sips up to a glass of water in the recovery room. Feeding will commence within 6 hours following surgery, starting with clear liquids and advance to soft diet after 24 hours then to regular diet when tolerated. In this study, patients who have tolerated early feeding, stayed for three days, while those who did not stayed for 3.5 days.

In terms of relationship between influencing factors and length of stay: with age, statistical analysis showed that there is no significant relationship between

these variables. It is because ERAS protocol works among all age group resulting to homogenous recovery process and hospital length of stay. In the meantime, amid type of surgery and length of stay, the relationship between these variables is significant and proven to influence the length of hospital stay, so much the same with pre-operative fasting, type of analgesia, early ambulation and early nutrition, among gyne-oncology surgery patients.

PONV is the only post operative complication emerged in this study. The data showed that length of stay is longer (3.8 Days) in respondents with PONV in comparison to those without PONV with LOS of only 3 days. The analysis of the data in the level of improvement status in participants with PONV on the other hand, has showed an increased average in partial improvement with the total of 68%, while full improvement is only 31.5%. Meanwhile, 80% of participants without PONV has fully recovered and only 20% partially recovered, which means that PONV directly and negatively affects recovery and length of stay of patients under ERAS protocol in a specialist hospital in KSA.

Conclusion

Influencing factors such as age, type of surgery, pre-operative fasting and carbo loading, type of analgesia, early ambulation, early nutrition and post-operative complication has something to do with hospital length of stay. Therefore, it is when how meticulous ERAS protocol is followed and implemented the effective and quality is the outcome becomes.

Recommendations

It is proven in the study that patients under ERAS protocol gain physical function early and discharged from the hospital early. In nursing perspective, the workload is less stressful and lighter when patients can take care of themselves. Nurses can focus in more important tasks, making them work more effectively. This contributes to staff satisfaction, and when staff is satisfied the better work outcome they could make. In patient and family point of view, fast recovery, no complications and discharge home early means going back to the normal routine. The patient can again take their role in the family, go back to work, resume normal activities which also means high patient and family satisfaction. For the institution, early patient discharge is another bed available to cater another patient. Furthermore, less complications and less hospital length of stay is complementary to lower hospital cost.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Approval of Protocol

Institutional Review Board Office
National Registration Number (H-05-D002)

APPROVAL OF PROTOCOL

Research Center
King Khalid Medical City (RC-KKMC)

30/09/2019

Grace D. Catulay
ERAS coordinator, Staff Nurse
NPQC CO-chair
King Fahad Specialist Hospital-Dammam
GraceD.Catulay@kfsh.med.sa

Dear Ms. Catulay,

On 30/09/2019 the IRB reviewed the following protocol:

IRB Study Number	NED0315
Title	Effects of ERAS implementation in Gynecology surgery patients in KFSHD: ERAS and Length of Stay
Principle Investigator	Grace D. Catulay
Sub-Investigator(s)	NONE
Funding	KFSH-D
Type of Submission	Initial submission
Type of Review	Expedited
Documents Reviewed	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• GCP checklist.• Human subject initial review template• Research protocol submission checklist• Data collection v1.1 dated 26/09/2019• Study Protocol v1.1 dated 26/09/2019• Grace D. Catulay CV, NCBE Certificate

I am pleased to inform you that the IRB approves the protocol from **30/09/2019** to **29/09/2020** inclusive. Before **29/08/2020** or within 30 days of study completion, whichever is earlier, you are required to submit:

- A completed **CONTINUING REVIEW PROGRESS / STUDY CLOSURE REPORT** form
- The required documents as per the above mentioned form

Failure to seek continuing review approval before **29/09/2020** will result to the Approval's expiry to take effect on the indicated date.

In conducting this protocol, you are required to follow the policies and procedures of KFSH-D and the requirements listed in the INVESTIGATOR MANUAL.

IRB-NED0315

Page 1 of 2

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التاريخ * وزارة الصحة
المرفقات * صحة الشرقية

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APPENDIX B

Approval of Amendments

Institutional Review Board Office
National Registration Number (H-05-D002)

Research Executive Administration
King Khalid Medical City (REA-KKMC)

Approval of Amendments

24th June, 2020

Grace Catulay
Staff Nurse & ERAS Coordinator
King Fahad Specialist Hospital-Dammam
GraceD.Catulay@kfsh.med.sa

Dear Ms. Catulay,

The IRB acknowledges receiving, reviewing and approving the below mentioned documents

IRB Study Number	NED0315
Title	Improving Surgical Care through the Enhanced Recovery After Surgery Program among Gyne-oncology Surgery Patients at a Specialist Hospital in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
Principal Investigator	Grace Catulay
Co-Investigator(s)	None
Funding	KFSH-D
Type of Review	Continuing review
Documents Reviewed	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Modification Of IRB Approved Research dated 22 June 2020.• Study protocol version 1.3 dated 22 June 2020

Sincerely,

Eman Nassim Ali, MD, MSc, PhD
Chairperson, Institutional Review Board

KFSH-D Institutional Review Board is AAHRPP accredited, and operates according to ICH-GCP and applicable Saudi laws and regulations

IRB-NED0315

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Appendix C

Study Closure

Institutional Review Board (IRB)
National Registration Number (H-05-D002)
Tel: +966 13 8443333, Ext: 2978, 2903
Email: IRB@kfsh.med.sa

Research Center
King Khalid Medical City (RC-KKMC)
King Fahad Specialist Hospital-Dammam

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT OF PROTOCOL CLOSURE

15 March 2021

Grace Catulay
Staff Nurse & ERAS Coordinator, Outpatient Department
King Fahad Specialist Hospital –Dammam
GraceD.Catulay@kfsh.med.sa

Dear Ms. Catulay:

On 15/03/2021, the IRB reviewed the following protocol:

IRB Study Number	NED0315
Title	Effects of ERAS Implementation in Gynecology Surgery Patients in KFSH-D: ERAS and Length of Stay
Principle Investigator	Grace Catulay
Documents Reviewed	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Study closure form, dated 14/03/2021• Study summary, dated 14/03/2021

The IRB acknowledges your request for closure of the protocol, and considers it effective. As part of this action:

- The protocol is permanently closed to enrollment.
- All subjects have completed all protocol-related interventions.
- Collection of private identifiable information is completed.
- Analysis of private identifiable information is completed.
- In compliance with National Committee of Bioethics Article (10.36), an end of study report needs to be submitted to the IRB once available

Sincerely,

Eman Nassim Ali, MD, MSc, PhD
Chairperson, Institutional Review Board

KFSH-D Institutional Review Board is AAHRPP accredited, and operates according to ICH-GCP and applicable Saudi laws and regulations

IRB- NED0315

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Appendix D

Invitation to Participate in the Research Study (Arabic and English Translation)

دعوة للمشاركة بدراسة بحثية

تعبان البحث: [Click here to enter text.](#)

البحث الرئيسي: [Click here to enter text.](#)

تود أن نطلعك على دراسة بحثية نقوم بها. الدراسات البحثية هي الوسيلة لمعرفة المزيد عن أي شيء. نود معرفة المزيد عن الموضوع [أدرج موضوع الدراسة وصف أهدافها بلغة بسيطة]. أنت مدعو/ة للانضمام الى هذه الدراسة لأنك [لخص باختصار، الحالة أو الظروف التي تجعل هذا الفرد مؤهل للمشاركة بهذا البحث، لا تقم بسرد معايير الإدراج والاستبعاد].

إذا وافقت على المشاركة بهذه الدراسة، سوف يطلب منك أن [صف الإجراءات (كالاستبيانات، والأنشطة) وعدد الزيارات والإطار الزمني بجدارت مفهومة بسهولة من قبل المشارك البالغ].

صف المخاطر المحتملة (مثل المضايقات) بلغة بسيطة.

(اختر إحدى الخيارين أدناه واحذف الآخر)

1. (استخدم هذا الخيار إذا كان هناك فائدة مباشرة مرجوة للمشاركين بالبحث، تُرجى ملاحظة أن التعويض أو سداد المصاريف ذات الصلة بالبحث لا تعتبر فائدة للمشاركة) لا يمكننا أن نعدك بأي فائدة لك أو للآخرين جزاء انضمامكم لهذا البحث. ومع ذلك، ممكن أن تتضمن القوائد المحتملة (ولاً صف القوائد المباشرة المحتملة للمشارك، ومن ثم صف أي قوائد للآخرين أو للمجتمع ككل).

2. (استخدم هذا الخيار إذا لم يكن هناك أي قوائد محتملة مباشرة للمشاركين بالبحث) لا توجد قوائد من انضمامكم لهذا البحث. ومع ذلك، فالقوائد المحتملة للآخرين تشمل: (صف أي قوائد للآخرين أو للمجتمع ككل).

ليس عليك الانضمام إلى هذه الدراسة الأمر متروك لك. يمكنك أن توافق الآن وتغير رأيك لاحقاً. كل ما عليك القيام به هو أن تقول لنا أنك تريد التوقف. لن يغضب أي شخص إن كنت لا تريد المشاركة في الدراسة أو إذا شاركت بالدراسة وغرت رأيك في وقت لاحق وتوقفت.

قرارك بالمشاركة أو لا، لن يؤثر على وضعك العلاجي أو الوظيفي أو الدراسي.

قبل أن تقول نعم أو لا للمشاركة هذه الدراسة، فإننا سنرد على أية أسئلة لديك. إذا اشتركت بالدراسة، يمكنك طرح الأسئلة في أي وقت. كل ما عليك قوله للباحث أنه لديك سؤال.

إذا كان لديك أي أسئلة حول هذه الدراسة لا تتردد في الاتصال (أدرج اسم الباحث وأرقام الاتصال).

إذا قتت بتعبئة الاستبيان أدناه، فهذا يعني أنك توافق على المشاركة في هذه الدراسة البحثية.

لقد روجبت هذه الدراسة واعتُوت من قِبل لجنة أخلاقيات البحث بمستشفى الملك فهد التخصصي بالدمام وفقاً للوائح المعمول بها في المملكة العربية السعودية و التي تهدف إلى حماية حقوق مصلحة المشاركين في البحث. وممكنك التحدث إليهم عبر الهاتف: +966 1-3 844 2978 أو +966 1-3 844 2905 أو البريد الإلكتروني: IRB@kfsh.med.sa بخصوص أي مما يلي:

- أسئلتك، ومخاوفك، أو شكواك التي لم تتم إجابته عنها من قِبل فريق الدراسة.
- لا يُمكنك الوصول لفريق الدراسة.
- ترغب في التحدث إلى شخص ما إلى جانب فريق الدراسة.
- لديك أسئلة حول حقوقك كمشارك في الدراسة.
- ترغب في الحصول على معلومات أكثر حول هذه الدراسة أو إبداء أي ملاحظات.

Invitation to Participate in a Research Study

Protocol Title: Evaluation of Enhance Recovery after Surgery on Length of stay and post-operative complications among Gyne-oncology patients in a Tertiary hospital in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Principal Investigator: Grace D. Catulay

Pilot

Version #: [Click here to enter text.](#)

Date: [Click here to enter text.](#)

We want to tell you about a research study we are doing. A research study is a way to learn more about something. We would like to find out more about **the effects of enhanced recovery after surgery program**. You are being asked to join the study because **you are an adult gynaecology patient and will go for an elective admission for a surgical procedure guided by the protocol of ERAS program**.

If you agree to join this study, you will be asked to **answer questions about level of pain, feeling of nausea, headache and or dizziness and episodes of vomiting. Will come to visit every day while admitted from after the surgery to ensure compliance with early ambulation, effective breathing exercises with the use of Incentive spirometry and proper nutrition.**

Pain especially after 12 hours after surgery will not go completely with analgesics, but early ambulation is needed for the patient to perform to decrease or eliminate chances of complications.

Choose 1 of the 2 options below and delete the other:

[1. The benefit that ERAS program can give to you is to restore your independent functions quickly because you will recover faster after surgery and chances of post-operative complications are low if there is compliance to the protocol. Your participation in this study will contribute to the new knowledge that will be learned about this program and will help other surgical patients in the future.

You do not have to join this study. It is up to you. You can say okay now and change your mind later. All you have to do is tell us you want to stop. No one will be mad at you if you don't want to be in the study or if you join the study and change your mind later and stop.

Your decision to participate or not won't affect your medical care, employment or studentship status.

Before you say YES or NO to being in this study, we will answer any questions you have. If you join the study, you can ask questions at any time. Just tell the researcher that you have a question.

If you have any questions about this study please feel free to contact **Grace Catulay with mobile number 0566367576**

If you complete the survey below, it means that you agree to take part in this research study.

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) responsible for human subject's research at King Fahad Specialist Hospital in Dammam has reviewed this research project, and found it to be acceptable, according to applicable Saudi regulations designed to protect the rights and welfare of participants in research. You may talk to them at +966-1 3-844 2978 or +966-1 3-844 2903 or email: IRB@kfsh.med.sa for any of the following:

- Your questions, concerns, or complaints are not being answered by the research team.
- You cannot reach the research team.
- You want to talk to someone besides the research team.
- You have questions about your rights as a research subject.
- You want to get further information or provide input about this research.

Appendix E

Data Collection Sample

109 Calculated field		1: Yes		0: No		9: Not Applicable														
		This field will be automatically calculated based on other entries																		
Specialty	Type of Surgical Procedure	MRN	Admission Date	Discharge Date	Surgery Date	Expected date of Discharge	Surgery Name	Surgery Type (Elective Vs. Urgent)	Primary Surgeon	First Anesthesiologist	Anesthesia Start Time (Induction)	Surgery Start Time	Surgery End Time	Anesthesia End Time	Anesthesia Duration	Surgery Duration	Intraoperative Blood Transfusion	HT	WT	BMI
GYNE	OPEN SURGERY																			
	LAPAROSCOPIC/MIS																			
	EXCLUDED																			

Anemia Screening Done	Anemia Management		Hb Value on Screening	Hb Value Immediately Before Surgery	Hb Value Immediately After Surgery	Creatinine		Nutritional Screening Done	Assessment of Physical Activity	Patient Read ERAS Passport		Patient Got Bowel Preparation	Carbohydrate load ordered	Gabapentin Ordered	Pre-operative Warming Done	Anti-septic Mouth wash done	Anti-septic Shower Done	Temperature maintained ≥ 36	Blood Sugar maintained between 4 - 10	Heparin 5000 IU Administered	Prophylaxis antibiotics administered with 60 minutes prior incision
	IV iron	Oral Iron				Pre Op	Post Op			Before Admission	Before Surgery										

					Outcome Indicators									
24 Hours Postoperatively Out of Bed 6 hours after surgery	24 Hours Postoperatively Pain Score Less Than 5/10	24 Hours Postoperatively Feeding started according to schedule (Soft Diet)	24 Hours Postoperatively Folly's Catheter Removed	Return of bowel movement	Re admission in 30 days	PONV in the First 24 hours Postoperatively	PONV Anytime Postoperatively (after 24 hours Postoperatively and during admission)	Paralytic Ileus during Admission	SSI within 30 Days after Surgery	Pneumonia (during admission)	CAUTI (during admission)	VTE within 30 days after discharge	LOS (Admission to Discharge)	LOS (Surgery date to discharge)

Appendix F

ERAS Protocol Form

مستشفى الملك فهد التخصصي بالدمام
King Fahad Specialist Hospital - Dammam

ANESTHESIA DEPARTMENT
GYNECOLOGY ERAS PROTOCOL

Name: _____
MR #: _____
DOB (dd/mm/yyyy): _____
Gender: Male Female

		ANESTHESIA	SURGERY	NURSING	PATIENT (to be filled by nurses)
Pre-operative Clinic	PREPARE	<input type="checkbox"/> Patient education <input type="checkbox"/> Discuss Thoracic Epidural for open surgery	<input type="checkbox"/> Patient Education <input type="checkbox"/> Anemia screening <input type="checkbox"/> Nutrition screening <input type="checkbox"/> Physical activity assessment <input type="checkbox"/> Stoma marking and teaching if applicable		<input type="checkbox"/> Education pamphlet <input type="checkbox"/> ERAS video Prehabilitation: <input type="checkbox"/> Anemia treatment program <input type="checkbox"/> Nutrition program <input type="checkbox"/> Exercise program <input type="checkbox"/> Have support at home in place for discharge.
	SIGNATURE & ID:				
DOS. PRE-OP	MEDICATIONS ANALGESICS	<input type="checkbox"/> Crystalloid @ 30 ml/hr. <input type="checkbox"/> Pre-Op Warming (forced air warmer in the holding area)	<input type="checkbox"/> NPO 8 hours before surgery except for the carbohydrate load and clear fluids <input type="checkbox"/> Carbohydrate load: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 800 ml at midnight before surgery <input type="checkbox"/> 400 at 6 am <input type="checkbox"/> NPO 2 hours before surgery Order placed for 6 am day of surgery: <input type="checkbox"/> Gabapentin 400mg PO* <input type="checkbox"/> Paracetamol 1000mg PO <input type="checkbox"/> Oral Bowel preparation if ordered by surgeon only	At 6 am day of surgery: <input type="checkbox"/> Morning mouth wash <input type="checkbox"/> Morning shower <input type="checkbox"/> Measure RBS and keep 4-10 mmol/L <input type="checkbox"/> Crystalloid started @ 30ml/hr. <input type="checkbox"/> Apply forced air warmer to Patient in the holding area	<input type="checkbox"/> NPO for 8 hours before surgery except for carbohydrate solution and clear fluids <input type="checkbox"/> Carbohydrate load: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 800 ml at midnight before surgery <input type="checkbox"/> 400 at 6 am <input type="checkbox"/> Complete NPO 2 hours before surgery
	SIGNATURE & ID:				
INTRA - OP	Medications	<input type="checkbox"/> Maintain patients temp more than or equal to 36°C <input type="checkbox"/> Measure RBS after induction, keep RBS 4-10 mmol/L <input type="checkbox"/> OG tube to low intermittent suction <input type="checkbox"/> Heparin 5000 IU SC, One (1) hour after epidural placement	<input type="checkbox"/> ERAS review during sign in		
	IVFs	Fluids targeting euvolemia: <input type="checkbox"/> MIS (robotic or laparoscopic) 1-2 ml/kg/hour balanced crystalloids. <input type="checkbox"/> ASA 1& 2 complicated open surgeries: GDFT or 6 ml/kg/hour balanced crystalloids. <input type="checkbox"/> ASA 3 or more open surgery GDFT (use Flowtrack or Masimo, keep SVV/PVI Less than 15%)			
	ABX	<input type="checkbox"/> Antibiotic: according to SSI IPP		Note: *Decrease Gabapentin dose to 200mg in patients with eGFR less than 40 or age more than 60 years.	
	PONV	<input type="checkbox"/> Dexamethasone 4 mg IV during induction <input type="checkbox"/> Metoclopramide 10mg IV before extubating unless contraindicated. <input type="checkbox"/> Ondansetron 4mg IV		Abbreviations: ERAS: Enhanced recovery after surgery IU: international units GDFT: Goal directed fluid therapy SVV: stroke volume variation PVI: pulse volume index MIS: minimally invasive surgeries (laparoscopic and robotic) TAP: Transverse abdominis plane block QHS: every night at bed time POD: post-operative day	
	ALL	<input type="checkbox"/> Minimize opioid medications, if necessary use only short acting <input type="checkbox"/> If Opioid-Tolerant, consult APS consultant			
	MIS	<input type="checkbox"/> Lidocaine IV infusion @ 2 mg/kg/hr. <input type="checkbox"/> Magnesium bolus 30 mg/kg (over 30 minutes) <input type="checkbox"/> TAP block at the end of surgery	<input type="checkbox"/> Surgeon infiltration 0.25% bupivacaine if no TAP block		
Pain Management	Open	<input type="checkbox"/> Thoracic Epidural at T8-12 Ropi/Bupivacaine 0.0625% +/- Fentanyl One (1) mcg/ml @ 8 ml/hr. or <input type="checkbox"/> TAP block or/and <input type="checkbox"/> lidocaine infusion or/and <input type="checkbox"/> Magnesium bolus <input type="checkbox"/> IV PCA only if indicated	<input type="checkbox"/> ERAS review during sign out		
SIGNATURE & ID:					

Form No.: 109/119 (Rev-0)
April 2019

GYNECOLOGY ERAS PROTOCOL – KF5HD
Page 1 of 2

Name: _____
MR #: _____
DOB (dd/mm/yyyy): _____
Gender: Male Female

Anesthesia Department
GYNECOLOGY ERAS PROTOCOL

PACU	MEDICATION	ANESTHESIA	SURGERY	NURSING	PATIENT (to be filled by nurses)
	REGIONAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Minimize opioid medications <input type="checkbox"/> Crystalloids: One (1) ml/kg/hr. <input type="checkbox"/> Thoracic Epidural 0.0625% Ropi/ Bupivacaine +/- Fentanyl One (1) mcg/ml @ 8 ml/hr. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Minimize opioid medications <input type="checkbox"/> Fluids: One (1)ml/kg/hour
Signature & ID:		Signature & ID:		Signature & ID:	
FLOOR/ICU POD (0)	MEDICATIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Gabapentin 400mg PO QHS* <input type="checkbox"/> Paracetamol 1000mg IV Q6H <input type="checkbox"/> Morphine 5-10 mg PO PRN Q4H for pain <input type="checkbox"/> Metoclopramide 10mg IV regular Q6H <input type="checkbox"/> Ondansetron 4mg IV PRN Q6H 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Immediate Post Op Labs on selected patients only <input type="checkbox"/> Full diet as tolerated <input type="checkbox"/> Bisacodyl 10 mg PO OD PRN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Out of bed 6 hours after surgery with assistance of Nursing <input type="checkbox"/> Incentive spirometry x 10 Q One H <input type="checkbox"/> Foley removal ASAP POD 4/5 (if pelvic dissection) <input type="checkbox"/> DVT Prophylaxis: Clexane 40mg PM (12 hrs. after surgery) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Out of bed within 6 hours after surgery <input type="checkbox"/> Incentive Spirometry x10 Q One H. <input type="checkbox"/> Unlimited clears. Advance to full diet as tolerated
	REGIONAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Thoracic Epidural 0.0625% Ropi/ Bupivacaine +/- Fentanyl One (1) mcg/ml @ 8 ml/hr. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Fluids: One(1)ml/kg/hour until PO is tolerated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Monitor epidural according to acute pain protocol 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Target is to have tolerable pain
Signature & ID:		Signature & ID:		Signature & ID:	
FLOOR/ICU POD (1-2)	MEDICATIONS		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Discontinue IV fluid once oral is tolerated <input type="checkbox"/> Full diet <input type="checkbox"/> Gabapentin 400mg PO QHS* <input type="checkbox"/> Paracetamol (1000) mg PO Q6H <input type="checkbox"/> Morphine 5-10 mg PO PRN Q4H <input type="checkbox"/> Ondansetron 4mg PO PRN Q6H <input type="checkbox"/> Metoclopramide 10mg PO PRN Q6H 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Ambulation, 6 x per day. At least first time with nurse <input type="checkbox"/> Ambulation, Out of bed to chair (3hrs.) BID <input type="checkbox"/> Incentive Spirometry x10 Q One H <input type="checkbox"/> DVT Prophylaxis: Clexane 40mg PM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Walking at least 6 times a day outside the room. At least first time with nurse. <input type="checkbox"/> Out of bed to chair (3hrs.) BID <input type="checkbox"/> Incentive Spirometry x10 Q One H <input type="checkbox"/> Full diet
	REGIONAL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> If Opioid-Tolerant, consult the acute pain service <input type="checkbox"/> POD (1): continue Epidural. <input type="checkbox"/> POD (2 or 3): assess for epidural removal. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Foley removal ASAP POD (4/5) (if pelvic dissection) 		
Signature & ID:		Signature & ID:		Signature & ID:	
FLOOR/ICU Discharge	MEDICATIONS		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Discharge instructions <input type="checkbox"/> Multimodal analgesia medications <input type="checkbox"/> Opioid only if needed <input type="checkbox"/> Plan for staples, drains, follow up labs appointment in place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Discharge instructions <input type="checkbox"/> Discharge medications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Ensure questions answered <input type="checkbox"/> Check follow up appointment date and time <input type="checkbox"/> Confirm plan in place for drains, staples pain meds, other meds, follow up <input type="checkbox"/> Support at home in place for discharge
	Signature & ID:		Signature & ID:		Signature & ID:

Appendix G

Physicians Order Form

مستشفى الملك فهد التخصصي بالدمام
 King Fahad Specialist Hospital - Dammam

Name: _____
 MR #: _____
 DOB (dd/mm/yyyy): _____
 Gender: Male Female

Date/Time	PHYSICIAN ORDERS			Initials of Healthcare Provider noting the order
Initials	Print name	Position	ID	

Form No.: 100/100 (Rev-1)
 October 2013

 PHYSICIAN ORDER SHEET – KFSHD
 Page 1 of 2

Appendix H

Pain and Re assessment Form

مستشفى الملك فهد التخصصي بالدمام
King Fahad Specialist Hospital - Dammam

Name: _____

MR #: _____

DOB (dd/mm/yyyy): _____

Gender: Male Female

**NURSING SERVICES
PAIN – ASSESSMENT/REASSESSMENT**

Date:	Time:	Date:	Time:
PAIN SCORE: _____ Tool Used: <input type="checkbox"/> Acute <input type="checkbox"/> Chronic <input type="checkbox"/> Both Character: _____ Frequency: _____ Location: _____ Duration: _____ Intervention: _____ Time: _____ Reassessment Post Intervention: * Time: _____ *Note: 15 - 30 minutes post IV/IM medication 30 - 60 minutes post oral medication PAIN SCORE: _____ TOOL: _____ Reassessment of Pain/Outcome: (Patients own words)		PAIN SCORE: _____ Tool Used: <input type="checkbox"/> Acute <input type="checkbox"/> Chronic <input type="checkbox"/> Both Character: _____ Frequency: _____ Location: _____ Duration: _____ Intervention: _____ Time: _____ Reassessment Post Intervention: * Time: _____ *Note: 15 - 30 minutes post IV/IM medication 30 - 60 minutes post oral medication PAIN SCORE: _____ TOOL: _____ Reassessment of Pain/Outcome: (Patients own words)	
☺ or ☹ Signature & ID Number: _____		☺ or ☹ Signature & ID Number: _____	
PAIN SCORE: _____ Tool Used: <input type="checkbox"/> Acute <input type="checkbox"/> Chronic <input type="checkbox"/> Both Character: _____ Frequency: _____ Location: _____ Duration: _____ Intervention: _____ Time: _____ Reassessment Post Intervention: * Time: _____ *Note: 15 - 30 minutes post IV/IM medication 30 - 60 minutes post oral medication PAIN SCORE: _____ TOOL: _____ Reassessment of Pain/Outcome: (Patients own words)		PAIN SCORE: _____ Tool Used: <input type="checkbox"/> Acute <input type="checkbox"/> Chronic <input type="checkbox"/> Both Character: _____ Frequency: _____ Location: _____ Duration: _____ Intervention: _____ Time: _____ Reassessment Post Intervention: * Time: _____ *Note: 15 - 30 minutes post IV/IM medication 30 - 60 minutes post oral medication PAIN SCORE: _____ TOOL: _____ Reassessment of Pain/Outcome: (Patients own words)	
☺ or ☹ Signature & ID Number: _____		☺ or ☹ Signature & ID Number: _____	

☺ If patient states pain free, pain at acceptable level or demonstrates no pain behaviors then reassess PRN

☹ If patient still in pain, or exhibiting pain behavior, reassess.

TOOLS: Numeric Pain Scale (N) Wong-Baker Face (WB) Comfort Scale (CS) FLACC (F)

Pain Assessment Tool for Advanced Dementia (AD)

Appendix I

Daily Physical Assessment Adult Form

مستشفى الملك فهد التخصصي بالدمام
King Fahad Specialist Hospital - Dammam

NURSING SERVICES DAILY PHYSICAL ASSESSMENT ADULT

Name: _____
MR #: _____
DOB (dd/mm/yyyy): _____
Gender: Male Female

DATE: _____ I. = Basic Assessment done two per 24 ^h . May be done more frequently as indicated. Variances, Interventions, & outcomes must be documented. II. = Advanced assessment - Optionally done as indicated	ASSESSMENT PARAMETERS: ✓ = assessment done - findings within the established criteria above * = assessment done - findings outside of established criteria; details charted and added to plan of care. Referrals made when indicated				
	Time / Initial and ✓ or *				
A. "Neurological Assessment" I. Pupils equal & reactive to light. Facial movement symmetrical. Alert and oriented to person, place and time. Behavior appropriate to situation. Verbalization clear and understandable. II. If advanced assessment, use <u>Neurological Assessment Form</u> . Mark this area with an asterisk to indicate Neurological Assessment Form is being utilized. <input type="checkbox"/> Non Applicable					
B. "Cardiovascular Assessment" I. No chest pain. Regular apical rate. CRT less than 2 sec. No edema. Peripheral pulses palpable (hands & feet).					
C. "Respiratory Assessment" I. No. SOB Respirations 12-20 min. at rest. Resp. regular. Breath sounds clear through both lung fields. No adventitious sound. Sputum clear if present. Nail beds and mucous membranes pink. II. If O ₂ saturation < 90% Inform MD. <input type="checkbox"/> Non Applicable					
D. "Neurovascular Assessment" I. Extremities are pink, warm and move within expected ROM. CRT less than 2 sec. Peripheral pulses palpable. No edema. Sensation intact without numbness or paresthesia. II. If condition/diagnosis requires frequent CMS (Circulation Motion Sensation) checks outside routine assessment implement Neurovascular Check Sheet. Mark this area with an asterisk to indicate Neurovascular Sheet is being utilized. <input type="checkbox"/> Non Applicable					
E. "Gastrointestinal Assessment" I. Abdomen soft. Bowel sounds active (5-34 per min). Having BMs within normal pattern & consistency. No nausea or vomiting. Passing flatus. No visible masses. No pain with palpation. For ostomies-stoma is pink, moist and skin intact. Document color and consistency of discharge from stoma. II. If NG present - it is patent. Document amount and color of output. <input type="checkbox"/> N/A					
F. "Nutritional Assessment" I. Tolerates prescribed diet without nausea or vomiting. Normal skin turgor. Well nourished. Swallows without coughing or choking on liquids or solids. No difficulty chewing. II. a If assessment reveals concerns in regards to swallowing obtain MD order for swallow evaluation to Speech Therapy. <input type="checkbox"/> Non Applicable II. b If assessment reveals concerns in regards to nutrition refer to Dietitian. <input type="checkbox"/> Non Applicable					
G. "Genitourinary Assessment" I. Voids without dysuria. Urine clear and within expected color range. Bladder not distended after void. If menses present: amount of flow is not greater than stated normal. II. If catheter present: color pale yellow to yellow, no sediment. <input type="checkbox"/> N/A					
H. "Teaching/Learning Assessment" (complete once every 24 hours or as needed) I. Understands and follows instructions. Asks appropriate questions regarding diagnosis and care. No barriers to teaching i.e., age, language, cultural, readiness, psychosocial. II. If assessment reveals concerns in regards to teaching/learning follow referral criteria to Health Education. <input type="checkbox"/> Non Applicable					
Initials	Signature/ ID#	Initials	Signature/ ID#	Initials	Signature/ ID#

Form No.: 200/071 (Rev-1)
May 2016

ADULT TREATMENT FLOW SHEET / DAILY PHYSICAL ASSESSMENT / PAIN ASSESSMENT/REASSESSMENT – KFSDH

Page 2 of 4

NURSING SERVICES
DAILY PHYSICAL ASSESSMENT ADULT

Name: _____
MR #: _____
DOB (dd/mm/yyyy): _____
Gender: Male Female

DATE: _____

I. = Basic Assessment done two per 24^h. May be done more frequently as indicated. Variances, Interventions, & outcomes must be documented.
II. = Advanced assessment - Optionally done as indicated

ASSESSMENT PARAMETERS:
✓ = assessment done - findings within the established criteria above
* = assessment done - findings outside of established criteria; details charted and added to plan of care, and other forms as indicated. Referrals made when indicated.

	Time / Initial and ✓ or *																							
	08:00		09:00		10:00		11:00		12:00		13:00		14:00		15:00		16:00		17:00		18:00		19:00	
I. "Culture, Values & Beliefs"																								
I. Voices no concerns																								
J. "Psychosocial"																								
I. Pt. communicates needs. Appropriate affect and interaction. Exhibits no behaviors that potentially harm self or others or interrupt necessary medical/surgical treatment. If asterisk refer to Social Services.																								
K. "Pain Assessment"																								
I. Patient pain free or states pain at an acceptable level. Demonstrates no pain behaviors. Tools: Numeric (N) Wong-Baker (WB) Comfort (C) Adv. Dementia (AD) FLACC (F)	Score																							
✓ No pain intervention needed * Pain intervention needed	Tool																							
"Infection / Isolation"																								
I. Isolation precautions indicated: <input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Neutropenic <input type="checkbox"/> Contact <input type="checkbox"/> Airborne <input type="checkbox"/> Droplet ✓ if isolation precautions are maintained * If changes during shift document Multidisciplinary Progress Notes																								
II. Resistant Organism: <input type="checkbox"/> MRSA <input type="checkbox"/> VRE <input type="checkbox"/> MDRO <input type="checkbox"/> Other	Site:																							
M. "Integumentary Assessment"																								
I. Skin color within expected norm. Skin warm, dry and intact. Mucous membranes moist. No redness, blisters, open areas, lesion, rashes or pressure ulcers																								
II. Type and character of wound drainage: Surgical incision: No redness or swelling. <input type="checkbox"/> Non Applicable																								
Mark this area with an * to indicate Wound/Ulcer Assessment sheet in use.																								
N. "Braden Scale Assessment"																								
If ≤ 16, place an asterisk (*) and address on Nursing Plan of Care, implement preventative measures document interventions, and refer to Wound Care Team if needed. Remark. If revised during the same shift, document time and Initial with ✓ or *																								
Braden Scale : Risk Assessment Tool																								
					AM	PM																		
Sensory Perception	1. Completely Limited	2. Very Limited	3. Slightly Limited	4. No Impairment																				
Moisture	1. Constantly Moist	2. Moist	3. Occasionally Moist	4. Rarely Moist																				
Activity	1. Bed fast	2. Chairfast	3. Walks Occasionally	4. Walks Frequently																				
Mobility	1. Completely Immobile	2. Very Limited	3. Slightly Impaired	4. No Limitations																				
Nutrition	1. Very Poor	2. Probably Inadequate	3. Adequate	4. Excellent																				
Friction and Shear	1. Problem	2. Potential Problem	3. No Apparent Problem																					
High Risk < 11	Moderate Risk 12-14		Mild Risk 15-16		No Risk > 16																			
					TOTAL																			
O. "Fall Risk Assessment"																								
Heindrich II Tool																								
Risk Factor	Risk Points	Patient Score		Risk Factor	Risk Points	Patient Score																		
		AM	PM			AM	PM																	
Confusion/Disorientation/Impulsive	4			Ability to rise in 1 movement	0																			
Symptomatic Depression	2			Pushes up successfully in 1 attempt	1																			
Altered elimination	1			Multiple attempts but successful	3																			
Dizziness/Vertigo	1			Unable to rise without assistance	4																			
Patient receiving anti-epileptics	2			No sitter present	1																			
Patient receiving Benzodiazepines	1			Uses 'Arabic' style toilet at home	1																			
Male gender	1			Mattress on floor at home	1																			
Total Score:		AM	PM	A score of 5 or more indicates patient is a high fall risk. Document interventions in the Nursing Plan of Care.																				
Time: _____		Time: _____																						
P. "Fall Risk Reassessment"																								
Document interventions in the Nursing Plan of Care																								
Check what's applicable:	Time:	Time:	Time:																					
<input type="checkbox"/> Any change in the patient condition	_____	_____	_____																					
<input type="checkbox"/> Post procedural sedation or general anesthesia	New Score: _____	New Score: _____	New Score: _____																					
<input type="checkbox"/> Change in meds affecting a patient's status	High Fall Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	High Fall Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	High Fall Risk <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No																					
<input type="checkbox"/> Immediately post fall																								

GRACE DEOCAMPO CATULAY

(+966) 568367576

gracedcats@yahoo.com

GraceD.Catulay@kfsh.med.sa

Present Employer: King Fahad Specialist Hospital Dammam

Accreditations: CBAHI, JCIA, Magnet Recognized Hospital

Licensure:

Philippine Regulation Commission

Registration number: 0301888

Category: Nurse

Saudi Council of Health and Specialties

Registration number: 06-K-N-2119

Category: Nurse Specialist

Employment Information:

Hospital name: King Fahad Specialist Hospital – Dammam

Position: Clinical Nurse Coordinator- ERAS Program

From: May 12, 2019 Up to: Present

Address: P.O. Box 15215, Dammam 31444 K.S.A.

Duties and Responsibilities

- Coordinates the preparation of patients through preoperative education using enhanced recovery after surgery pathway (ERAS). Monitors patients to ensure continuity of care, from the time the operation is booked, before and during hospital admission, the day of surgery and immediate post-operative period, as required.
- Implements ERAS pathway and collaborates with multidisciplinary team in preparing protocols and patient educational materials. Performs daily rounds to monitor patient progress and ensure compliance to ERAS protocols. Serves as a liaison by collaborating with relevant departments involved in ERAS patients (i.e. anesthesiologists, surgeons, nurses and support staff).
- Performs data collection and clinical audit of ERAS program/s. Develops weekly reports or as required. Provides support to ERAS programs and activities, including educational initiatives, as required.
- Initiates and maintains professional interpersonal relationship by communicating effectively, positively and politely with patients and the multidisciplinary health care team to resolve problems and conflicts using organizational structures and processes, evidence-based interventions and culturally-sensitive solutions.
- Contributes to the identification of training needs relevant to the specialized area. Participates in the induction of new staff including the training related to the specialized area procedures and competencies. Participates in the in-service, continuing education and quality improvement programs.
- Maintains confidentiality relating to all matter dealt within the department. Uses great discretion at all times and ensure that no confidential material is disclosed from the department to unauthorized members of staff.

- Follows all hospital-related policies and procedures. Participates in emergency and disaster procedures. Performs other duties in the realm of my knowledge and ability as required.

Hospital name: King Fahad Specialist Hospital – Dammam

Area Assigned: Out patient Department

From: January 9, 2009 Up To: May 9, 2019

Address: P.O. Box 15215, Dammam 31444 K.S.A.

Duties and Responsibilities

- Plans and provides patient care according to patient needs, acuity level based on unit standards.
- Incorporates transcultural principles into nursing care.
- Communicates and/or documents all relevant information as per established standards.
- Strives to maintain positive professional multidisciplinary relationships.
- Monitors unit operations in conjunction with the Head Nurse including reporting equipment malfunction, safety and security issues, and/or supply availability.
- Participates and implements performance improvement activities/projects.
- Actively involved in patient education programs.
- Responsible for professional development based on self evaluation and peer review.
- Contributes to development, implementation and evaluation of unit activities.
- Act as a mentor to a newly hired staff.
- Support staff development and saudization.
- Complies with all hospital policies and procedures.
- Participates in Nursing Affairs and Quality management and Development Administration activities.
- Participates in Emergency and Disaster procedures.
- Performs other duties within the realm of my knowledge and ability as required.

Hospital/Clinic Name: Armed Forces Hospital King Abdulaziz Air base

Position: Surgery Clinic Nurse

Area Assigned: Out Patient Department - Surgery Unit

From: June 2004 To: June 2008

Address: Dhahran, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Duties and Responsibilities

- Responsible in gathering patient's data, vital signs and prepare patient for physical assessment for referral to physician or consultant.
- Prepares patient for admission, and assist in any diagnostic procedures.
- Give patient medication per oral, anal, injections or parenteral preparations according to doctor's order.
- Facilitates immediate referral to any hospital of choice or nearby hospital in case of uncontrollable medical condition.
- Responsible for providing patient nursing care in the clinic, setting in compliance with hospital policies and procedures.
- Works under the direction of the Supervisor/Head Nurse to coordinate unit activities and implement unit goals.

- Participates in all aspect of Nursing Department including staff orientation, quality improvement, continuing education, committee appointment or special projects as defined and assigned.
- May be assigned to the duties and responsibilities of the Head Nurse in her absence.
- Performs other applicable duties and tasks within the realms of her knowledge, skills and abilities as directed.

Hospital/Clinic Name: Al naim Polyclinic, Al hassa Hofuf KSA

Position: ER nurse

Area Assigned: ER, ophthalmology, urology, internal medicine clinic

From: April 2001 To: April 2003

Address: AL hassa, Hofuf, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Duties and Responsibilities

- Rotating area of assignment from different clinics. Rendering different kinds of skills and knowledge to deal in many cases as well as to assist and perform clinical procedures.
- Triage patient conditions by observation of symptoms, reaction, and reporting them to physicians.
- Perform therapeutic measures prescribed and delegated by the medical authority such as:
 - assist in advance cardiopulmonary resuscitative measures.
- assists in the performance of minor invasive procedures of cut down lumbar puncture,
- prepare and assist the doctors in performing minor surgeries for an emergency
 - Assist in the deliveries and also performs actual deliveries alone for patient if need arises.
 - Responds to Code Blue Call when patient's needs to be resuscitated as part of emergency team.
 - Conduct ambulance duty in accident sites and transport patients to other hospital for further care and management.
 - Response to emergency Disaster Calls when needed in major casualties such as: accident and crash calls.
 - Assist in the orientation of new staff with on the job training.
 - Assist in the proper admission of patients and coordinates with other members of the health team prior to patient transfer to ward.
 - Maintain professional and ethical conduct at all times

Hospital/Clinic Name: L.N. Agustin Memorial Mission Hospital

Position: Female/Male Surgical Nurse

Area Assigned: Medical Surgical Ward, Pediatric ward, OB-Gyne ward

From: June 1997 To: December 2000

Address: Mandalagan, Bacolod City Negros Occidental, Philippines

Duties and Responsibilities

- Provide nursing care to patients within assigned unit in support of the medical plan of care and consistent with the nursing care plan in compliance with the nursing department.
- Perform nursing assessment on every patient.
- Observes and reports changes to Head nurse for the patients condition and response to treatment.
- Initiate and performs a range of nursing measures base on patient needs related to physical and mental comfort, positioning and mobilization, nutrition and hydration, bowel and bladder

elimination, care of skin and wounds, and support of respiration, hygiene, communication and other physical and mental bodily function.

- Provide safe therapeutic personalized physical psychological environment for patient care.
- Assists in the formulation of nursing care standard policy.
- Support the Head nurse and Staff in the implementation of nursing care standards and policies.
- Reports documents significant information through established oral and written process.
- Participates in aspects in areas of total nursing program such as, patient care conference, staff orientation, quality assurance, or special projects as defines and assigned for specific period of time.

Educational Information:

Post Graduate: Master of Arts in Nursing

UP Open University
June 2012 To: Present (Currently working on Thesis)
Laguna, Philippines

College: Bachelor of Science in Nursing

Colegio San Agustin-Bacolod
June 1991 To: March 1995
B.S. Aquino Drive Bacolod City Negros Occidental

Eligibility:

Licensure Taken: National Board Examination

Date of Exam: November 30, 1995

Score: 77.60

License Validity: renewable in 3 years
2012

From: February 6, 2006 **To:** June 16,

Place of Exam: Cebu City